

VVM Glossary

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Date of creation October 13, 2023
Version 2023.10

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(Machine) Perception

Term German

Perzeption (maschinelle Wahrnehmung)

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Naming part of the [processing](#) chain (in the context of Sense-Plan-Act)

Explanation

Recording the [objects](#) that are relevant to the driving [task](#) and their properties/characteristics. This includes recording their own state. Recording is carried out via [sensor](#) channels and leads to a [world model](#) by means of interpretation.

Relation to other terms

[Sensor](#), [perception algorithm](#), [world model](#)

Delimitation from

Perception, interpretation of complex relationships, prediction

Source

VVM-internal modification of machine perception: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Machine_perception

Usage

Bosch / OFFIS, ZF

6-Layer Model

Term German

6-Ebenen-Modell

Intention

Description

Explanation

The six-layer model is a systematic, complete and consistent description of the scope of all [scenarios](#). It is both vertical, due to the addition of new layers, and horizontal, due to the addition of further parameters within a level, as well as being expandable and therefore adaptable to its future areas of application. Within the framework of PEGASUS, the model has been used to describe the scope of all motorway situations.

Related objects

[Scenarios](#)

Related subjects

Traffic participants, traffic environment, [scenario](#)

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model, traffic environment

Source

Pegasus [Project](#): https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/Pegasus-Abschlussveranstaltung/05_Scenario_Description_and_Knowledge-Based_Scenario_Generation.pdf

Usage

TP1

ADS Dual Mode Vehicle

Term German

ADS-Dual-Mode-Fahrzeug

Intention

Description

Explanation

An ADS dual-mode vehicle is a vehicle equipped with an [Automated Driving System](#) (ADS) that can be operated not only by a driver but also in driverless mode.

Source

SAE J3016 April 2021

ADS-Dedicated Vehicle

Term German

Mit ADS dediziertes Fahrzeug

Abbreviation

ADS-DV

Intention

Description

Explanation

An ADS-equipped vehicle that was developed specifically for driverless operation and is used exclusively in driverless mode.

Source

J3016:3.32.3 ADS-Dedicated Vehicle (ADS-DV) (2021/04)

Usage

All

Abstract Scenario

Term German

Abstraktes [Szenario](#)

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Abstract [scenarios](#) are used to describe, illustrate and derive [causal relations](#).

Explanation

An abstract [scenario](#) is a formalised, declarative description of a traffic [scenario](#) that focuses on describing complex relationships – especially [causal relations](#). The semantics of the description are based on ontology.

Related objects

Ontological entities

Related subjects

Automated vehicle, traffic participant

Subject (addressee)

Data collector, safety engineer

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#), ontology, [causal relation](#)

Delimitation from

Functional/logical [scenario](#)

Source

[Criticality](#) Analysis for the [Verification](#) and [Validation](#) of Automated Vehicles — IEEE Journals & Magazine — IEEE Xplore: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9330510>

Usage

TP2

Accident

Term German

Unfall

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Definition	Beispiel
Bedrohung (threat): mögliche Ursache eines unerwünschten Ereignisses, der einem System oder einer Organisation Schaden zufügen kann [ISO/TR 18638]	Steiles Gelände in der Nähe der Straßeneinführung bedroht die Unversehrtheit der Beteiligten
Gefahr (danger): gefährliche Situation, die, wenn sie nicht vermieden wird, zum Tod oder zu schweren Verletzungen führen kann [ISO 26513]	A: Steinschlaggefahr B: Gefahr von Eisglätte
Gefährdung (hazard): potential source of harm [ISO 26262, ...] (for a specific stakeholder)	Hz1A: Beschädigung der Fahrgastzelle durch herabfallende Steine Hz2A: Spurverlust & Verlassen der Fahrbahn durch Steine auf der Fahrbahn
Gefährliches Ereignis (hazardous event): combination of a hazard and an operational situation [ISO 26262]	Hs1H1A: Stein mit 100kg Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz während der Fahrt im Bereich des Fahrers Hs2H1A: Stein mit 1 kg Masse trifft Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz im Stillstand im Bereich des Befahrers
Schaden (harm): physische Verletzung oder Schädigung der Gesundheit von Personen oder der Beschädigung von Sachen [ISO/IEC Guide 51] <i>modified</i>	Verletzung der FZ-Massen durch 1. beschädigte Fahrgastzelle 2. Verlassen der Fahrbahn
Risiko (risk): Schadensmaß kombiniert mit Eintrittswahrscheinlichkeit [ISO/IEC Guide 51]	120 x Steinschläge/Jahr 10 % große Steine mit Verletzungspotential Verkehrsdichte 1:10 Scheibengröße 1:10 => 0,12 Verletzungsfälle/Jahr
Unfall (accident): Eintritt eines Schadens durch ein ungeplantes Ereignis [ISO 24765]	Tatsächlich verletzte Personen durch herabfallende Steine, welche die Windschutzscheibe eines Fz durchschlagen haben.

Explanation

Occurrence of **harm** due to an unintended event.

Related subjects

Subject vehicle, vehicle occupants, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

Risk

Delimitation from

Risk

Source

[ISO 24765]: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec-ieee:24765:ed-2:v1:en:term:3.43>
modified

Usage

TP3

Affiliation Metrics

Term German

Zugehörigkeitsmetrik

Intention

Measurement

Explanation

Affiliation [metrics](#) break down continuous [input data](#) into sections of logical basic [scenarios](#). Temporal overlaps between logical basic [scenarios](#) can mean that a vehicle finds itself in multiple logical [scenarios](#) at one point in time.

Relation to other terms

Algorithms and [metrics](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Allocation

Term German

Allokation

Intention

Description

Explanation

The [process](#) and result of distributing [requirements](#), resources or other entities among the components of a system or program.

Subject (addressee)

System [architecture](#)

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017 Systems and software engineering-Vocabulary; 3.130

Architecture

Term German

Architektur

Intention

Description

Explanation

See: [System architecture](#)

Source

See: [System architecture](#)

Architecture Level

Term German

[Architekturebene](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

See: [System level](#)

Source

See: [System level](#)

Argumentation Structure

Term German

Argumentationsstruktur

Intention

Description

Explanation

An argumentation structure is not a concrete [safety case](#) but rather a pattern/template that describes a substantive ranking aid for arguments and evidence types to support a [claim](#) in a concrete context, so that it is possible to trace the fulfilment of required characteristics such as completeness within the chosen context.

For example, the VVM argumentation structure sets out this pattern for the components of a [proof of release](#) (which are necessary from a VVM perspective) that is intended to meet with acceptance from the relevant stakeholders (licensing authority, society, ...).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Artifact

Term German

Artefakt

Intention

Description

Explanation

The term is used to refer to any – usually immaterial – representation of an entity. The artefact can be populated with any kind of information, such as meta-data, and can contain additional information and/or link to external content. Moreover, trace links can be used to establish traceability between individual artefacts.

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

ISO 15288 / ProSTEP

Usage

TRACY

Assessment Scale

Term German

Bewertungsmaßstab

Intention

Measurement

Intention detailed

Assessment scales classify standards (references) as being applicable to or usable for assessments (not measurements)

Example: Quality assessment standard: [-, -, o, +, ++]

Explanation

Assessment standards seek to limit the subjective component of assessments and, within certain limits, to facilitate the comparability of assessment results and assessed elements.

Assessment is different from measurement. Measurement delivers precise values with a tolerance. Assessment includes subjective components. There are [metrics](#) for both assessment and evaluation .

Related objects

Standards (references)

Related subjects

Assessing person or element

Subject (addressee)

Engineers, judges, licensing authority, all TPs

Relation to other terms

Standard, reference

Delimitation from

Standards for measured parameters (as opposed to assessment parameters)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

AP1.5; TP4, TP7; Bosch

Assurance Case

Term German

Assurance Case

Intention

Description

Explanation

Reasoned, auditable [artifact](#) created that supports the contention, that its top-level [claim](#) (or set of [claims](#)) is satisfied, including systematic argumentation and its underlying evidence and explicit assumptions that support the [claim\(s\)](#).

Note 1 to entry: An assurance case contains the following and their relationships:

- one or more [claims](#) about properties;
- arguments that logically link the evidence and any assumptions to the [claim\(s\)](#);
- a body of evidence and optionally assumptions supporting these arguments for the [claim\(s\)](#); and
- justification of the choice of top-level [claim](#) and the method of reasoning.

Source

ISO 15026-1:2019 Clause 3.1.2

Usage

Core03

Automated Driving System

Term German

Automatisiertes Fahrsystem

Abbreviation

ADS

Intention

Description

Explanation

The hardware and software that, together, are able to permanently carry out the entire dynamic driving [task](#) (DDT) regardless of whether it is limited to a specific [operational design domain](#) (ODD). This term is used in particular to describe an Automated Driving System of SAE Level 3, 4 or 5.

Note:

In contrast to ADS, the generic term "driving automation system" refers to all systems or functions of SAE Level 1 to 5 that permanently perform part or all of the DDT. Given the similarity between the generic term "driving automation system" and the specific term "Automated Driving System" for Levels 3 to 5, the latter should be capitalised and wherever possible reduced to its abbreviation, ADS, while the former should be left unabbreviated.

An ADS-equipped vehicle exists in two forms

1. ADS-DV, ADS dedicated vehicle: A vehicle of this kind is developed for permanent driverless operation and is therefore operated in a driverless manner on a permanent basis.
2. ADS dual-mode vehicle: A vehicle of this kind can be operated both by a driver and in driverless mode.

Related objects

Automated vehicle

Relation to other terms

Ego-vehicle

Delimitation from

Generic term for driving systems of SAE Level 1–5

Source

SAE J3016 April 2021

Automated Driving System Equipped Vehicle as Product

Term German

Mit ADS ausgestattetes Fahrzeug als Produkt

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

- One key difference between ADS in traffic (one individual example of the vehicle) and ADS as a product (the swarm of all the vehicles, whose returned data allows conclusions to be made about the product's characteristics) is the scope of consideration.
- Bodies involved in the product design [process](#) (e.g. management, engineering, etc.) are represented within the term "Organisation" and therefore come within the context of product, market, etc. The organisation must be capable of implementing a system that demonstrates the necessary capabilities for safe participation in road traffic – in accordance with the state of the art at SOP. To implement systems, the organisation draws on resources (systems, departments, ...). It must also equip itself to learn from the systems in operation (vehicle in traffic) and to adapt the systems' capabilities continually and roll out improvements immediately.
- Collecting data via the ADS in traffic is just one example implementation of how changes in the environment can be detected or corresponding assumptions can be tested. There may also be other ways of implementing this capability.
- In the past, it was the driver who realised the capability of detecting changes in the open context and, consequently, of operating safely. From Level 3 upwards, this capability must be provided by the system because the driver is out-of-the-loop. It is therefore necessary for the manufacturer to implement this capability. One way of detecting changes in the open context is to use the swarm of vehicles as "[sensors](#)" in order to collect and return data. It is important to note that this is not a question of releasing an unfinished product, but rather of implementing an additional capability.
- Storyline valid not only for changes in the context but also for all other things that must be considered following deployment in order to ensure the product's safety on a lasting basis (e.g. changes in laws → new road sign, system performance monitoring → e.g. tests of perception performance with regard to design-time assumptions).

Explanation

An ADS-equipped vehicle as a product is the validated result of a product design [process](#) that considers the challenges of the open context.

One key difference between an ADS-equipped vehicle in traffic (one individual example of the vehicle) and as a product (the (sub)fleet of all the vehicles, whose returned data allows conclusions to be made about the product's characteristics) is the scope of consideration, with a focus on the individual vehicle or on the traffic situation.

Delimitation from

ADS-equipped vehicle in traffic

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Automated Driving System Equipped Vehicle in Traffic

Term German

Mit ADS ausgestattetes Fahrzeug im Verkehr

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

- Main motivation of ADS in traffic: When it comes to deployment, we have insufficient confidence (i.e. residual uncertainty) that the safety can be ensured on a lasting basis over the lifecycle without post-deployment measures. The argumentation must therefore ensure that sufficient efforts are made to ensure safety at the time of deployment. However, changes in the context must also be expected after deployment, and this understanding must be taken into account explicitly in the [safety argumentation](#) and through post-deployment monitoring.
- Use in relation to [safety argumentation](#): Falsification of assumptions, confirmation of assumptions, recording of new facts/edge cases
- Implication for [architecture](#): Methods for collecting evidence must be designed within the context of the product and implemented in traffic. In particular, this calls for architectural elements that primarily provide field data for the purpose of testing assumptions rather than contributing directly to fulfilment of the target behaviour. If necessary, shadow mode can also be used during non-automated operation to falsify specific assumptions of the product design. Shadow mode in an ADS in traffic is one example implementation of a falsification capability.
- ADS in traffic and ADS as a product form a control loop: An ADS in traffic, as a swarm of individual vehicles, offers the possibility of using situations recorded in the field to validate product characteristics (primarily safety aspects) and to adapt them if necessary (related to the capability for "learning"). Example: Following deployment, an ADS in traffic acts according to the target behaviour, i.e. the product carries an acceptable residual [risk](#), taking account of all existing safety-relevant insights in accordance with SotA and SotP. The capability for learning ensures that valid target behaviour can be maintained over the whole product lifecycle, especially in the case of unpredictable context changes after deployment (product context, e.g. new law, incomplete [requirements](#); or traffic context, e.g. new traffic participants, detected edge cases, [accidents](#), change in behavioural norm).

- Which assumptions are falsified? Adherence to specified target behaviour at runtime, [verification](#) of assumptions regarding context that were used when specifying the target behaviour, such as the surprise arrival rate (Surprise Metrics (Metrics Episode 12):: <https://safeautonomy.blogspot.com/2020/12/surprise-metrics-metrics-episode-12.html>)
- In a "generalised" product lifecycle, e.g. of a mobility service provider with an internal company organisation, there may be (a need for) further ways of maintaining the operational capabilities (see e.g. current draft of the "Level 4 Law" (Act amending the Road Traffic Act and the Compulsory Insurance Act – Autonomous Driving Act), NHTSA Incident Reporting: Standing General Order 2021-01).

Explanation

With regard to safety, an [Automated Driving System](#)-equipped vehicle (ADS) in traffic is a safety-validated example of a product in the concrete traffic situation, in which it is supposed to act according to the [requirements](#) (target behaviour).

An ADS-equipped vehicle in traffic can optionally allow the collection of field information in order to respond to the challenges of the open context.

Delimitation from

ADS-equipped vehicle as a product

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Automation Risk

Term German

Automationsrisiko

Intention

Description

Explanation

Automation [risk](#) refers to the [risk](#) induced or caused by an automated driving function. The automated vehicle therefore represents the primary cause of an [accident](#). This does not include deficits in effectiveness, such as an insufficient response in [scenarios](#) induced by third parties.

Related objects

[System under Test](#)

Related subjects

Ego vehicle, traffic participant

Relation to other terms

General, automation function

Source

Identifikation und Quantifizierung von Automationsrisiken für hochautomatisierte Fahrfunktionen (pegasusprojekt.de): https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/pdf/PEGASUS_TechnicalReport_Automationsrisiken_17.07.2019.pdf

Usage

TP1

Backend

Term German

Backend (Datenbank)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The backend is a series of algorithms that operate in the background and invisibly to the user, representing the interface between database and [frontend](#).

Related objects

Database

Related subjects

Data

Relation to other terms

Database

Source

Pegasus Glossar

Usage

TP1

Capability Architecture (Organization)

Term German

Fähigkeiten [Architektur](#) (Organisation)

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

The capability [architecture](#) provides a common language that describes the world using clear terminology and allows a company/organisation to collaborate effectively across functional boundaries by way of simple statements.

Explanation

Architectural definition of a set of organisational capabilities, with [leaf-level](#) capabilities aligned to needs, and their measures.

Source

https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Enterprise_Capability_Management: https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Enterprise_Capability_Management

Usage

AP3.4

Capability Layer

Term German

Capability Layer

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Differentiation between various perspectives on the SuT. The various perspectives are accompanied by different problem domains and/or solution spaces. By naming the layer in a current [task](#), it is therefore possible to avoid misunderstandings.

Explanation

The capability layer provides a perspective for describing capabilities of the organisation and system. Capabilities enable a methodical approach to effective release argumentation on an abstract level.

The artefacts of the capability layer provide the basis for an abstract argument as to why the system's capabilities for implementing safe behaviour in the open context are sufficiently specified and the V&V concept can provide sufficient evidence for delivering those capabilities.

Core aspects:

- Delimitation of [engineering layer](#): The capability layer is an abstract layer that describes the problem domains; the [engineering layer](#) is a technical layer that describes solution domains.
- Consideration of organisation and automated system with the same capabilities concept → This results in a need to differentiate between ADS in traffic (→ automated system) and ADS as a product (→ organisation).

Related objects

[System under test](#)

Delimitation from

[Engineering layer](#), [real world layer](#), [6-layer model](#)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Causal Chain / Effect Chain

Term German

Wirkkette

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Causal chains describe a chronological, plausible/causal series of events.

Explanation

A causal chain is a [causal relation](#) in which each successive event has only one predecessor. It is not possible to represent events taking place in parallel.

Related objects

One-dimensional, plausible/causal sequence of events

Related subjects

Events, traffic participants, time, relations

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researcher, traffic planner, test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Criticality](#) analysis, traffic situation, traffic [scenario](#)

Delimitation from

[Criticality phenomenon](#), [causal relation](#)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2; OFFIS, Bosch, ZF

Causal Relation

Term German

Wirkzusammenhang

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Causal relations describe plausible causalities (e.g. how [criticality](#) develops in a traffic [scenario](#))

Explanation

Series of events in a traffic [scenario](#), partially ordered with respect to their temporal occurrence and continuation so that the simultaneity of preceding events is plausible/causal for the subsequent event. It is possible for events to take place in parallel.

Related objects

[Causality](#) of events over an extended period of time

Related subjects

Events, traffic participants, time, relations

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researcher, traffic planner, test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Criticality](#) analysis, traffic situation, traffic [scenario](#)

Delimitation from

[Criticality phenomenon](#), causal chain

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2; OFFIS / Bosch, ZF

Causality

Term German

Kausalität

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

The relationship between cause and effect.

Explanation

Causality is the relationship between events and states, with the enactment of the cause bringing about the effect. In this regard, one cause can lead to multiple effects or multiple causes can lead to one effect.

Related objects

[Causal relationship](#)

Related subjects

Cause, effect, relation

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researchers, experts, scientists, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

[Plausibility](#), [criticality](#), [causal relation](#), causal chain

Delimitation from

Correlation

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2; OFFIS / Bosch, ZF

Challenger

Term German

Challenger (Herausforderer oder Störobjekt)

Intention

Description

Explanation

A challenger is a vehicle (Layer 4) whose behaviour/presence provokes a reaction from the [vehicle under test](#).

The behaviour of the [vehicle under test](#) can also be influenced by more than one challenger.

On the proving ground, the challenger is identical to the TSV that compels the [vehicle under test](#) to take direct action.

Related objects

Traffic participants

Related subjects

Ego vehicle, traffic participants, traffic environment

Relation to other terms

General, traffic environment

Delimitation from

Ego vehicle, TSV

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de), Systematic Identification of Scenarios: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Claim

Term German

Anspruch

Intention

Benennen

Explanation

A claim is a true-false statement about the limitations on the values of an unambiguously defined property — called the claim’s property — and limitations on the uncertainty of the property’s values falling within these limitations during the claim’s duration of applicability under stated conditions.

Note 1 to entry: Uncertainties may also be associated with the duration of applicability and the stated conditions.

Note 2 to entry: A claim potentially contains the following:

- property of the system-of-interest;
- limitations on the value of the property associated with the claim (e.g., on its range);
- limitations on the uncertainty of the property value meeting its limitations;
- limitations on duration of claim’s applicability;
- duration-related uncertainty;
- limitations on conditions associated with the claim; and
- condition-related uncertainty.

Note 3 to entry: The term ”limitations” is used to fit the many situations that can exist. Values can be a single value or multiple single values, a range of values or multiple ranges of values, and can be multi-dimensional. The boundaries of these limitations are sometimes not sharp, e.g., they can involve probability distributions and can be incremental.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 15026-1:2019(en): Systems and software engineering — Systems and software assurance — Part 1: Concepts and vocabulary; 3.1.4: claim

Usage

Core03

Completeness (Scenario Strand)

Term German

Vollständigkeit (Szenarienstrang)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Completeness ([scenario](#) strand): The set of logical [scenarios](#) is able to describe the test cases within the framework of the selected ODD

- **Claim:** Further observation of the world does not lead to further new logical [scenarios](#)

Delimitation from

[Coverage](#)

Source

VVM internal

Concept of Operations

Term German

Concept of Operations

Abbreviation

ConOps

Intention

Description

Explanation

At the organisation level, the ConOps refers to how the leadership intends to run the organisation.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018(en): 3.1.5 Concept of Operations: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/fr/#iso:std:iso-iec-ieee:29148:ed-2:v1:en>

Usage

Core03

Concern

Term German

Concern

Intention

Description

Explanation

An interest in a system relevant to one or more of its stakeholders.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 42020:2019 Software, systems, and enterprise–[Architecture processes](#)

ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015 Systems and software engineering–System life cycle [processes](#)

Concrete Scenario

Term German

Konkretes [Szenario](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

A concrete [scenario](#) arises from the instantiation of a logical [scenario](#) through the assignment of concrete values.

Relation to other terms

[Scenarios](#)

Source

Bagschik et al. (2017): Szenarien für Entwicklung, Absicherung und Test von automatisierten Fahrzeugen: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/de/information-material?file=files/tmp1/pdf/Walting_Szenarien%20fuer%20Entwicklung%20Absicherung%20Test%20Abstract.pdf

Usage

TP1

Configuration Item

Term German

Konfigurationsgegenstand

Intention detailed

Description

Explanation

The term configuration item (CI) describes any entity of a system that serves the purpose of configuration management. It can therefore be used as a placeholder for a real system element (hardware, software, etc., combination, etc.) at any point in a system and holds configuration-relevant data. It has a unique identifier that can be referred to elsewhere (e.g. in baselines).

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

ISO 15288

Usage

TRACY / ProSTEP

Controllability

Term German

Kontrollierbarkeit

Intention

Measurement

Explanation

The controllability of a [scenario](#)/[scene](#) indicates how hard it is to manage without an [accident](#) occurring. It therefore also implicitly indicates the necessary driving capabilities of the system driving the vehicle or of the driver.

Relation to other terms

Algorithms and [metrics](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Coverage

Term German

Abdeckung

Intention

Measurement

Explanation

The term coverage is used in VVM as a fundamentally quantifiable indication of the coverage of the ODD through test cases and reasoning (related to the validity space of the sampling method).

There are three levels of coverage:

1. [Scenarios](#)/ [scenario](#) concepts
 - (a) Is the concept capable of coverage?
2. Existing [scenarios](#) / ODD description
 - (a) Have all characteristics been recorded based on the data?
3. Have we selected enough test cases from this to be able to make a statement?

Source

VVM internal

Criticality

Term German

Kritikalität

Intention

Evaluation + measurement

Intention detailed

Criticality predictively assesses the total [risk](#) for the remainder of a traffic situation.

Explanation

Criticality (of a traffic situation) is the combined [risk](#) of the involved actors when the traffic situation is continued.

Remark 1: In order to determine criticality, probabilities and types of [harm](#), dynamical and behavioural models and actions restrictions of the involved actors are taken into account.

Remark 2: The time horizon of criticality of a traffic situation is bound by the fulfilment of the involved actors' intentions.

Remark 3: Criticality is inversely correlated with the amount of (sequences of) actions to avoid [harm](#) that are available to the involved actors.

Criticality (of a [scenario](#)) can be defined by aggregating the criticality of a time sequence of traffic situations.

Remark 4: For example, using the maximum or an average over a discrete number of time steps.

Related objects

[Risk](#), [accident](#) probability, [accident severity](#), traffic situation

Related subjects

Traffic participant, observer

Subject (addressee)

Traffic participant, [accident](#) researcher, test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

Criticality analysis, traffic situation, traffic [scenario](#)

Delimitation from

Risk, danger, hazard

Source

Criticality Analysis for the [Verification](#) and [Validation](#) of Automated Vehicles
— IEEE Journals & Magazine — IEEE Xplore: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9330510>

Usage

TP2

Criticality Analysis Domain

Term German

Suchbereich der Kritikalitätsanalyse

Abbreviation

CAD

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Term used to designate the [coverage](#) area of a [criticality](#) analysis

Explanation

Part of the traffic space examined by a [criticality](#) analysis

Related objects

Things in road traffic

Related subjects

Automated vehicle, traffic participant

Subject (addressee)

Experts, [project](#) planner, safety engineer

Relation to other terms

[Criticality](#), [criticality](#) analysis

Delimitation from

[Operational design domain](#) (ODD), use case

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2; OFFIS

Criticality Metric

Term German

Kritikalitätsmetrik

Intention

Assessment

Intention detailed

A [criticality](#) metric evaluates the [criticality](#) of a traffic situation or [scenario](#).

Explanation

(Mathematical) function or algorithm that assesses the [criticality](#) of a traffic situation using available parameters.

Related objects

Any variables

Related subjects

[Subject vehicle](#), traffic participants, traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researcher, test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Criticality](#), [criticality](#) analysis, traffic situation, traffic [scenario](#), algorithm, metric

Delimitation from

Metric

Source

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11831-022-09788-7>: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11831-022-09788-7>

Usage

TP1

Criticality Phenomenon

Term German

Kritikalitätsphänomen

Abbreviation

KP/CP

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Describes phenomena in the traffic [scene](#) that the perceiver evaluates as critical.

Explanation

A [criticality phenomenon](#) is a concrete [influencing factor](#) (or a combination of [influencing factors](#)) in a traffic [scenario](#) that is associated with increased [criticality](#).

Related objects

[Influencing factor](#), observation

Related subjects

Traffic participants, experts (ontology)

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researcher, traffic planner, test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Criticality](#) analysis, traffic situation, traffic [scenario](#)

Delimitation from

[Criticality](#), [criticality](#) measure, [criticality](#) metric, [influencing factor](#)

Source

[Criticality](#) Analysis for the [Verification](#) and [Validation](#) of Automated Vehicles — IEEE Journals & Magazine — IEEE Xplore: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9330510>

Usage

TP2

Criticality Threshold

Term German

Kritikalitätsschwellwert

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

A [criticality](#) threshold allows the classification of traffic situations and [scenarios](#) with regard to [criticality](#).

Explanation

For a given [criticality](#) metric and traffic situation or [scenario](#), a [criticality](#) threshold quantifies the boundary between critical and non-critical.

Related objects

Situation, [scenario](#), [criticality](#) metric

Related subjects

[Subject vehicle](#), traffic participants, traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researcher, test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Criticality](#), [criticality](#) analysis, traffic situation, traffic [scenario](#), algorithm, metric, [criticality](#) metric, classification

Source

VVM internal

Usage

OFFIS

Cross-Cutting-Concern

Term German

Cross-Cutting-[Concern](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

A [concern](#) that cannot initially be separated at will and that requires coordination between multiple solution providers.

Source

Wikipedia: Cross-cutting [concern](#): https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cross-cutting_concern

Database Mechanics

Term German

Datenbankmechanik

Intention

Description

Explanation

The database mechanics are the sum total of the [processing](#) steps and applied algorithms and [metrics](#) that take place between the input and output of data to/from the database. Here, in addition to other [processing](#) steps, primarily logical/concrete [scenarios](#) are extracted and then abstracted by means of attribution and parameterisation and made available for output. This can therefore also be referred to as a database [processing](#) chain. Input and output are exclusive in this regard.

Related objects

Database

Related subjects

Ego-vehicle, system components

Subject (addressee)

Data

Relation to other terms

General, [subject vehicle](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Decomposition

Term German

Dekomposition

Intention

Description

Explanation

Decomposition of a system/function into subsystems/subfunctions. In the context of the [project](#), this specifically refers to the decomposition of an automation function into functional levels (e.g. according to Graab et al.: information access, information reception, information [processing](#), behavioural decision and action).

Related objects

[System under Test](#)

Relation to other terms

General, automation function

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Demand-Reinforcing Factor

Term German

[Anforderungs](#)verstärkender Faktor

Intention

Description

Explanation

A demand-reinforcing factor is an event or circumstance that does not constitute a challenging [scenario](#) in itself but that leads to increased [requirements](#) and/or action constraints if the vehicle is forced to react by another challenging, [scenario](#)-inducing factor. Examples of demand-reinforcing factors include a wet roadway or a narrow traffic lane.

Relation to other terms

Logical [scenario](#), [scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [Glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Driver Equivalent (Human)

Term German

Fahreräquivalent (Mensch)

Intention

Comparing

Intention detailed

This term is intended to help compare the many aspects of humans in road traffic – perception, intention, capabilities and expectations – with a machine. This comparison should be carried out using problem-oriented abstraction from experience-based or theoretically obtained insights.

Explanation

For a specific context (e.g. a traffic [scenario](#)), the driver equivalent establishes a comparative relationship between human drivers and automated driving functions with respect to the ([requirements](#),) actions and capabilities for performing the driving [task](#). The [entirety of the] behavioural patterns of human drivers are abstracted by modelling, taking particular account of the dimensions of perception, intention, capabilities, expectations, legal duties and standard behaviour.

Related objects

Automaton, traffic rules

Related subjects

Driver

Subject (addressee)

TP2 ([Criticality](#) analysis), TP3, TP4 (Functions), TP7 (Test)

Relation to other terms

Capability, perception, law, intention, expectation

Delimitation from

Statistical variables such as average driver behaviour, individual performance values

Source

Schwarz et al. (2022): Measuring Safety: Positive Risk Balance & Conscientious Driver: https://www.vvm-projekt.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Mid-Term/VVM_HZE_S1_P4_20220315_MeasuringSafety.pdf

Usage

TP3

Driver Equivalent (Machine)

Term German

Fahreräquivalent (Maschine)

Intention

Comparing

Intention detailed

This term is intended to help compare the many aspects of humans in road traffic – perception, intention, capabilities and expectations – with a machine. This comparison should be carried out using problem-oriented abstraction from experience-based or theoretically obtained insights.

Explanation

Obtained via the [driver equivalent \(human\)](#), the driver equivalent (machine) is the representation of human drivers and provides the basis for checking equivalence with the machine representation/the digital twin of the automated driving function. The driver equivalent is fulfilled if the automated function (machine representation) achieves a defined and demonstrable maximum deviation from the driver representation in the considered comparative dimensions.

Related objects

Automaton, traffic rules

Related subjects

Driver

Subject (addressee)

TP2 ([Criticality](#) analysis), TP3, TP4 (Functions), TP7 (Test), VVM, judges

Relation to other terms

Prediction, perception, mission, driving [task](#), performance

Delimitation from

Statistical variables such as average driver behaviour, individual performance values

Source

Schwarz et al. (2022): Measuring Safety: Positive Risk Balance & Conscientious Driver: https://www.vvm-projekt.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Mid-Term/VVM_HZE_S1_P4_20220315_MeasuringSafety.pdf

Usage

TP3

Driving Demand Metrics

Term German

Fahranforderungsmetrik

Intention

Measurement

Explanation

In each time step of the [input data](#), the driving demand [metrics](#) assess the driving demands on the human driver or automated driving function as result of the traffic constellation. Especially in a changing environment (e.g. due to the roadway geometry or other traffic participants), these [metrics](#) take account of the required reaction time, options for getting out of the way, and the braking potential in order to avoid an [accident](#).

Relation to other terms

Algorithms and [metrics](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Emergent Property

Term German

Emergente Eigenschaft

Intention

Naming

Explanation

A property of a system of elements that cannot be derived from the properties of the individual elements.

Source

Rausand M, Haugen S (2020) [Risk](#) Assessment: Theory, Methods, and Applications, 2. Aufl. Wiley, Hoboken. doi:10.1002/9781119377351, S. 97

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Engineering Layer

Term German

Engineering Layer

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Differentiation between various perspectives on the SuT. The various perspectives are accompanied by different problem domains and/or solution spaces. By naming the layer in a current [task](#), it is therefore possible to avoid misunderstandings.

Explanation

The engineering layer provides a perspective for describing the solution architecture of the organisation and system. This perspective-oriented [architecture](#) enables effective release argumentation on the technical level.

The artefacts of the engineering layer provide the basis for an argument as to why the generated solution leads to the delivery of capabilities by means of systematic engineering methods in the modelled context and why the results of the implemented V&V concept ("Technical V&V Design") can be relied upon with regard to the delivery of capabilities in the modelled context.

Core aspects

- We're in the solution space
- Controlled environment through modelling based on assumptions
- "Classical" perspective-based automotive systems engineering
- [Technical design](#) of capabilities regarding vehicle behaviour and runtime monitoring/learning (delimitation from real world: the real world is [concerned](#) principally with returning data, analysis with a view to ensuring the capabilities and acceptable [risk](#), and the reaction to changed [risks](#), e.g. due to an [architecture](#) update)
- Modelled context relates to ODD, assumptions, [scenarios](#) in whose context engineering is carried out, i.e. it refers not only to modelling of the traffic context of the ensuing vehicle, but also to all other assumptions regarding system characteristics (e.g. necessary simulation model fidelity in order to successfully demonstrate the characteristic)

Related objects

[System under test](#)

Delimitation from

[Capability layer](#), real world wayer, 6 layer model

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Environment Model

Term German

Umfeldmodell

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

An environment model contains the environment part of the [world model](#) (without the part of the respective actor)..

Explanation

Representation of the environment based on perception.

Relation to other terms

Perception

Delimitation from

[World model](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Event (Traffic-)

Term German

Geschehnis (Verkehrs-)

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Categorical designation of all things that correspond to the explanation.

Explanation

Every change in the environment or in the state of automatons or people over time. The change needn't necessarily be perceptible or measurable. However, it must be real and not merely hypothetically or statistically expected.

Related objects

All things and creatures in the environment

Related subjects

All creatures

Subject (addressee)

VVM, public, judges

Relation to other terms

Time, physics, procedure, [processes](#), development

Delimitation from

Static condition, invariance

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP3

Exposure

Term German

Exposure

Intention

Measurement

Explanation

Exposure is a distance- or time-oriented frequency at which events occur in a logical or (semi-)concrete [scenario](#).

For example, the exposure could be a frequency of parameter values for a [scenario](#) parameter, or the frequency of whole [scenarios](#) in one or more recorded datasets.

Relation to other terms

Algorithms and [metrics](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Frontend

Term German

Frontend (Datenbank)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The frontend of the database is a website, available at www.pegasus.fka.de: <http://www.pegasus.fka.de/>, that serves as the interface with the database for users.

Related objects

Database

Related subjects

Data

Relation to other terms

Database

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Functional Architecture

Term German

Funktionale [Architektur](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Hierarchical arrangement of functions, their internal and external (external to the aggregation itself) functional interfaces and external physical interfaces, their respective functional and performance [requirements](#), and their design constraints.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017 Systems and software engineering-Vocabulary

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Functional Design

Term German

Funktionales Design

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Process and result of defining the working relationships among the components of a system. In this case, the term **components of a system** refers to functional elements of a system.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017 Systems and software engineering-Vocabulary:

”**Process** and result of defining the working relationships among the components of a system.”

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Functional Domain

Term German

Funktionale Domäne

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Structuring of activities for system development

Explanation

Solution-independent space for considering content and scopes to fulfil a functionality from the user's perspective.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Functional Requirement

Term German

Funktionale [Anforderung](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Statement identifying what results a product or [process](#) must produce.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765f:2016

Functional Safety Concept

Term German

Funktionales Sicherheitskonzept

Abbreviation

FSC

Intention

Naming

Explanation

The functional safety concept references safety-related parts of the [functional design](#) and describes their necessary interaction to achieve the [safety goals](#).

Source

Based on ISO 26262

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Functional Scenario

Term German

Funktionales [Szenario](#)

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

[Scenario](#) description with a focus on comprehensibility to humans.

Explanation

A functional [scenario](#) is a behaviour-based natural-language description of a [scenario](#) at the semantic level (possibly including visualisation).

Related objects

Ontological entities

Related subjects

Automated vehicle, traffic participant

Subject (addressee)

Experts, reviewers, [project](#) partners

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#), ontology

Delimitation from

Logical/abstract [scenario](#)

Source

Bagschik et al. (2017): Szenarien für Entwicklung, Absicherung und Test von automatisierten Fahrzeugen: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/de/information-material?file=files/tmp1/pdf/Walting_Szenarien%20fuer%20Entwicklung%20Absicherung%20Test%20Abstract.pdf

Usage

TP1 / TP2

Functional Test Requirement

Term German

Funktionale Testanforderung

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Specific element of a functional artefact that should be covered by functional testing.

Source

Based on ISO/IEC 26554:2018 Information technology–Software and systems engineering–Tools and methods for product line testing:

”Specific element of a domain (functional) [artifact](#) that should be covered by domain (functional) testing.”

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Functional Test Specification

Term German

Funktionale Testbeschreibung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Detailed (complete, precise, verifiable) formulation to describe [requirements](#) for determining characteristic functional properties according to the functional [requirements](#) for a specific purpose.

Among other things, the functional test specification includes:

- [scenario](#) (incl. declared parameters & variation specifications)
- test [object](#) (functional test element)
- functional [requirements](#) (incl. qualities & confidences)
- [test class](#)/method (used as metainformation)
- other guidelines for test orchestration (representativity, e.g. in the form of standards, movement patterns or material properties of individual elements)

Note:

The functional test specification is not executable and serves as an input to then be assigned to the elements of the [technical design](#) and the [test instances](#) (see [technical test specification](#)).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 / AG10

Functional Use Case

Term German

Funktionaler Anwendungsfall

Abbreviation

FUC

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

The aim is to outline the functionality investigated in the [project](#) and the functional range of a driving function by way of example so that [project](#) partners can evaluate and demonstrate their [validation](#) methods.

Explanation

The functional use case describes a potentially infinite quantity of interaction sequences, i.e. functional use case [scenarios](#) that occur between various actors. These interactions take place in an environment and are described by at least one step. During such a sequence, a primary actor pursues [objectives](#) relating to the environment, always including a primary [objective](#). This is the common point of reference for all interaction sequences in the functional use case, which therefore represent an abstract property or functionality of the primary actor. For more information, see accompanying document Functional Use Case.

Related objects

[Scenarios](#) and functionality

Related subjects

Traffic participants, environmental conditions, behaviour, [objectives](#)

Subject (addressee)

VVMethoden partners

Relation to other terms

[6-layer model](#), customer function, functional [requirement](#), item definition

Delimitation from

SSimulation use case (SET Level term), (functional/abstract) [scenario](#)

Source

VVM extension of ISTQB Glossar: Anwendungsfall: <https://www.testautomatisierung.org/testglossar-test-deutsch/>

Usage

Alle TPs

Glossary

Term German

Begriffsregister

Intention

Naming

Explanation

This document

Ground Truth Data

Term German

Ground Truth Daten

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various data types (data types according to data table)

Explanation

Ground truth data is of the same abstraction level as "environment model data", albeit of significantly higher accuracy. This data is assumed to provide a sufficiently accurate reflection of reality.

Related objects

Traffic environment

Related subjects

Traffic participants, traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP6/TP8; ika

Harm

Term German

Schaden (Sach- und Personenschäden)

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Explanation

Injury or damage to the health of people, or damage to property

Related subjects

Subject vehicle, vehicle occupants, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

Risk, probability, severity of harm

Delimitation from

Severity of harm

Source

[ISO/IEC Guide 51]: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec:guide:51:ed-3:v1:en:term:3.1>

Hazard

Term German

Gefährdung

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Definition	Beispiel
Bedrohung (threat): mögliche Ursache eines unerwünschten Ereignisses, der einem System oder einer Organisation Schaden zufügen kann [ISO/TR 18638]	Steiles Gebirge in der Nähe der Straßeneinführung bedroht die Unversehrtheit der Beteiligten
Gefahr (danger): gefährliche Situation, die, wenn sie nicht vermieden wird, zum Tod oder zu schweren Verletzungen führen kann [ISO 26513]	A: Steinschlaggefahr B: Gefahr von Eisglätte
Gefährdung (hazard): potential source of harm [ISO 26262, ...] (for a specific stakeholder)	Hz1A: Beschädigung der Fahrgastzelle durch herabfallende Steine Hz2A: Spurverlust & Verlassen der Fahrbahn durch Steine auf der Fahrbahn
Gefährliches Ereignis (hazardous event): combination of a hazard and an operational situation [ISO 26262]	Hs1H1A: Stein mit 100kg Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz während der Fahrt im Bereich des Fahrers Hs2H1A: Stein mit 1 kg Masse trifft Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz im Stillstand im Bereich des Befahrers
Schaden (harm): physische Verletzung oder Schädigung der Gesundheit von Personen oder der Beschädigung von Sachen [ISO/IEC Guide 51] <i>modified</i>	Verletzung der FZ-Massens durch 1. beschädigte Fahrgastzelle 2. Verlassen der Fahrbahn
Risiko (risk): Schadensmaß kombiniert mit Eintrittswahrscheinlichkeit [ISO/IEC Guide 51]	120 x Steinschläge /Jahr 10 % große Steine mit Verletzungspotential Verkehrsdichte 1:10 Scheibengröße 1:10 => 0,12 Verletzungsfälle/Jahr
Unfall (accident): Eintritt eines Schadens durch ein ungeplantes Ereignis [ISO 24700]	Tatsächlich verletzte Personen durch herabfallende Steine, welche die Windschutzscheibe eines Fz durchschlagen haben.

Explanation

Potential source of **harm** (for a specific stakeholder)

Related subjects

Subject vehicle, vehicle occupants, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

Danger, **risk**, probability, **severity of harm**

Delimitation from

Threat, danger, **risk**, **accident**

Source

[ISO 12100, ISO 26262, ...] modified

Hazardous Event

Term German

Gefährliches Ereignis

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Definition	Beispiel
Bedrohung (threat): mögliche Ursache eines unerwünschten Ereignisses, der einem System oder einer Organisation Schaden zufügen kann [ISO/TR 18638]	Steiles Gelände in der Nähe der Straßeneinführung bedroht die Unversehrtheit der Beteiligten
Gefahr (danger): gefährliche Situation, die, wenn sie nicht vermieden wird, zum Tod oder zu schweren Verletzungen führen kann [ISO 26513]	A: Steinschlaggefahr B: Gefahr von Eisglätte
Gefährdung (hazard): potential source of harm [ISO 26262, ...] (for a specific stakeholder)	Hz1A: Beschädigung der Fahrgastzelle durch herabfallende Steine Hz2A: Spurverlust & Verlassen der Fahrbahn durch Steine auf der Fahrbahn
Gefährliches Ereignis (hazardous event): combination of a hazard and an operational situation [ISO 26262]	Hs1H1A: Stein mit 100kg Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz während der Fahrt im Bereich des Fahrers Hs2H1A: Stein mit 1 kg Masse trifft Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz im Stillstand im Bereich des Befahrers
Schaden (harm): physische Verletzung oder Schädigung der Gesundheit von Personen oder der Beschädigung von Sachen [ISO/IEC Guide 51] <i>modified</i>	Verletzung der FZ-Massen durch 1. beschädigte Fahrgastzelle 2. Verlassen der Fahrbahn
Risiko (risk): Schadensmaßmaß kombiniert mit Eintrittswahrscheinlichkeit [ISO/IEC Guide 51]	120 x Steinschläge/Jahr 10 % große Steine mit Verletzungspotential Verkehrsdichte 1:10 Scheibengröße 1:10 => 0,12 Verletzungsfälle/Jahr
Unfall (accident): Eintritt eines Schadens durch ein ungeplantes Ereignis [ISO 24795]	Tatsächlich verletzte Personen durch herabfallende Steine, welche die Windschutzscheibe eines Fz durchschlagen haben.

Explanation

Combination of a **hazard** with an operating situation.

Note: **Scenarios** support the description of operating situations.

Related subjects

Subject vehicle, vehicle occupants, traffic participants, elements of the **scenario**

Relation to other terms

Hazard, situation, **scenario**

Delimitation from

Danger, **hazard**, **risk**, **accident**, situation, **scenario**

Source

[ISO 26262]: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso:26262:-1:ed-2:v1:en:term:3.77> 1.59 "hazardous event"

Usage

TP3

Influencing Factor

Term German

Einflussfaktor

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Categorisation of factors that influence traffic situations (e.g. [criticality](#))

Explanation

Factor (parameter) that influences a traffic situation

Related objects

Everything in the traffic [scene](#)

Related subjects

Traffic participants

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researcher, traffic planner, test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Criticality](#) analysis, traffic situation, traffic [scenario](#)

Delimitation from

[Phenomenon](#), [criticality phenomenon](#), [causal relation](#), causal chain

Source

Westhofen (2023): [Criticality Metrics](#) for Automated Driving: A Review and Suitability Analysis of the State of the Art: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11831-022-09788-7>

Usage

TP2; OFFIS, Bosch, ZF

Infrastructure Ground Truth

Term German

Infrastructure Ground Truth

Abbreviation

IGT

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various types of data

Explanation

Data of the type "ground truth data" sourced from infrastructure [sensors](#). The data must meet defined standards.

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with information on traffic [scenes](#)

Relation to other terms

Aerial ground truth, Dynamic Ground Truth, [simulated ground truth](#)

Delimitation from

[World model](#), [vehicle top box](#) raw data labels, [environment model](#) data

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2,3,4,5,6,7,8; ika

Input Data

Term German

Eingangsdaten (Datenbank)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Input data is the data uploaded into the PEGASUS database in PEGASUS input data format and that is [processed](#) there by the [database mechanics](#).

For example, this can include FOT, NDS, [accident](#) or simulation data. The data must at least meet the [requirements](#) of the minimal dataset.

Relation to other terms

Input and output data

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Intended Behavior (SotiF)

Term German

Verhaltensanforderungen (SotiF)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Specified behaviour of the intended functionality, including interactions with the environment.

Source

ISO 21448:2022 3.13

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Layer 1 - Road Network and Traffic Guidance Objects

Term German

Layer 1 - Straßennetzwerk und verkehrsleitende [Objekte](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Layer 1 describes the physical characteristics of the road. These include the roadway geometry and topology as well as the road surface. The layer also includes a definition of the quality and boundaries within the layer.

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Layer 2 - Roadside Structures

Term German

Layer 2 - Randbebauung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Layer 2 describes where and how vehicles are driven on the roadway within the applicable traffic rules.

Layer 2 supplements Layer 1 with the physical boundaries of the roadway in the form of crash barriers and of lanes in the form of lane markings (lines, nail road blocks, ...) as well as with traffic signs and applicable traffic rules including, for example, instructions from the police.

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Layer 3 - Temporary Modifications of Layer 1 and 2

Term German

Layer 3 - Temporäre Änderungen der Ebenen 1 und 2

Intention

Description

Explanation

Layer 3 describes temporary influences on or limitations of the roadway area. These include: roadworks markings (e.g. roadworks beacons, temporary lane markings), spilled loads, fallen trees, dead animals, etc.

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Layer 4 – Dynamic Objects

Term German

Layer 4 - Dynamische [Objekte](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Layer 4 describes the behaviour and movement of relevant dynamic [objects](#) in relation to the VUT that potentially and actually influence the behaviour and movement of the automated vehicle. These include other vehicles, pedestrians, etc., that are in motion relative to the vehicle.

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Layer 5 - Environmental Conditions (Road Weather)

Term German

Layer 5 - Umweltbedingungen

Intention

Description

Explanation

Layer 5 describes how system performance is influenced by environmental conditions, such as rain or light conditions. These can influence the properties of other layers. For example, parameters include light conditions (brightness, glare, ...), weather (rain, snow, fog, ...) and temperature.

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Layer 6 - Digital Information

Term German

Layer 6 - Digitale Informationen

Intention

Description

Explanation

Layer 6 describes the quality and availability of relevant digital information or its disruptive effect on the VUT or the [system under test](#). This information can induce or influence a [scenario](#) and can be made available via V2X communication or via data storage in the vehicle. It also includes digital maps and [backend](#) servers.

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Layers of a Scenario

Term German

Layer eines [Szenarios](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

A layer represents a descriptive level of a [scenario](#). A complete [scenario](#) description consists of six layers (roadway geometry, guidance infrastructure, temporary influences, dynamic [objects](#)/traffic participants, environmental conditions, digital information).

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Lead Vehicle Challenger (A)

Term German

Vorausfahrer (A)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The lead vehicle **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/object that was in the vehicle path in front of the VUT at the start of the **scenario** approaches the front of the VUT.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**, **scenario** model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN ([pegasusprojekt.de](https://www.pegasusprojekt.de)), Systematic Identification of Scenarios: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Leaf-Level

Term German

Blattebene

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Used to illustrate the definition of capability [architecture](#)

Explanation

The lowest level in a hierarchy structure. The leaves do not contain any successor and are usually the most specific elements in the hierarchy.

Source

OLAP.com: <https://olap.com/learn-bi-olap/olap-bi-definitions/leaf-level/#:~:text=What%20is%20Leaf%20Level%3F,Members%20or%20Leaf%20Level%20Members.>

Usage

AP 3.4

Logical Domain

Term German

Logische Domäne

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Technology-independent space for considering content and scopes of a functionality with consideration not only of the [functional domain](#) but also of non-functional [requirements](#) (keyword: RAMST, including reliability, availability, manufacturability/maintainability, safety/security, testability) from the developer's perspective.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4/7 AG1/SB1

Logical Scenario

Term German

Logisches [Szenario](#)

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

[Scenario](#) description with a focus on expanding a [parameter space](#) and machine readability.

Explanation

Model of a chronological sequence of [scenes](#) that begins with a starting [scene](#) and whose parameters have defined value ranges.

Related objects

Ontological entities

Related subjects

Automated vehicle, traffic participant

Subject (addressee)

Experts, [project](#) planner, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Scenario](#), [parameter space](#), parameter

Delimitation from

Functional/abstract/concrete [scenario](#), [scene](#)

Source

Bagschik et al. (2017): Szenarien für Entwicklung, Absicherung und Test von automatisierten Fahrzeugen: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/de/information-material?file=files/tmp1/pdf/Walting_Szenarien%20fuer%20Entwicklung%20Absicherung%20Test%20Abstract.pdf

Usage

TP1

Logical Scenario Class

Term German

Logische Szenarienkasse

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

More-detailed specification of the term "logical [scenario](#)", as there is a significant difference between the level of a "logical [scenario](#)" as a declaration and that of a "logical [scenario](#)" as a concrete [scenario](#) with distributions instead of concrete values.

Explanation

Declaration of a logical [scenario](#) (sequence and attribute/parameter declaration). Also includes parameter boundaries, dependencies, etc., that are already clear prior to population with data and that declare the logical [scenario](#).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP8

Logical Scenario Concept

Term German

Logisches Szenarienkonzzept

Intention

Description

Explanation

The logical [scenario](#) concept is a systematic description of the traffic or traffic area within a parameterised space. It allows unique classification of relations and should record them fully enough to allow a [validation process](#). The concept is made up of numerous logical [scenario](#) classes.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP8

Logical Scenario Instance

Term German

Logische Szenarien Instanz

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

More-detailed specification of the term "logical [scenario](#)", as there is a significant difference between the level of a "logical [scenario](#)" as a declaration and that of a "logical [scenario](#)" as a concrete [scenario](#) with distributions instead of concrete values.

Explanation

The logical [scenario](#) instance is a populated logical [scenario](#) class. In other words, the [scenario](#) belongs to the class and populates all of the declared parameters with concrete distributions. These distributions can also be the trivial distribution and therefore semi-concrete or even concrete [scenarios](#).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP8

Measurement Data

Term German

Messdaten

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Recorded information on measurements produced by one or more different measuring systems, measuring instruments or measuring devices.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Measurement-Data Scenario

Term German

[Messdatenszenario](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

A [measurement data scenario](#) represents a concrete [scenario](#), recorded in a real environment, that was extracted from an [input dataset](#) based on [measurement data](#) and can be assigned to a logical [scenario](#) by the [database mechanics](#).

Relation to other terms

[Scenarios](#), special concrete [scenarios](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Metrics

Term German

Metrik

Intention

Measurement

Intention detailed

Metrics are intended to turn any given number of input values with any dimensions into a scalar value. This scalar value can then be used to assess or compare (complex) relationships that give rise to the input values.

Explanation

A metric is a function that generates a unique value from the given input values, e.g. measured quantities.

In VVM, this value is generally numerical and is used to assess or classify [scenarios](#).

Related objects

Any variables

Related subjects

[Subject vehicle](#), traffic participants, traffic environment

Relation to other terms

Algorithms and metrics

Delimitation from

Mathematical definition of metrics

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP1

Milestone

Term German

Meilenstein

Intention

Description

Explanation

Milestones typically refer to points in time at which new [phases](#) begin or at which major planned events or series of events are completed. Milestones generally also define "control gates", at which point (design) decisions must be made or reviews must be carried out.

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

ISO 15288 / ProSTEP

Usage

TRACY

Minimal Data Set

Term German

Minimaldatensatz

Intention

Description

Explanation

The minimal dataset defines necessary [input data](#) signals and [input data](#) qualities that must be present as a minimum to be able to ensure [processing](#) by the [database mechanics](#). Minimum frequencies and minimum accuracies are also defined.

Relation to other terms

Input and output data

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Mitigation Mechanism

Term German

Mitigationsmechanismus

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Description of an implication ("if X, then Y") whose application reduces the [severity](#) (or, in more general terms, the [risk](#)) of an [accident](#).

Explanation

Driving manoeuvres, courses of action or characteristics that, for example, reduce the [severity](#) of an unavoidable [accident](#) in a class of [scenarios](#).

Related objects

Driving manoeuvre, courses of action, characteristic

Related subjects

Automated vehicle, traffic participant

Subject (addressee)

[Requirements](#) engineer, traffic participant, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Causal relation](#), causal chain, [criticality](#), [safety goal](#), safety function, [safety principle](#), mitigation (safety)

Delimitation from

[Causal relation](#), causal chain, [safety goal](#), safety function, [safety principle](#), mitigation (safety)

Source

OFFIS, Bosch, ZF

Usage

TP2

Near Accident

Term German

Beinaheunfall

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Refers to a traffic situation of very high [criticality](#).

Explanation

A traffic situation in which it was only just (temporally or spatially) possible to avoid [harm](#).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2; OFFIS

Normative Argumentation

Term German

Normative Argumentation

Intention

Evaluation

Intention detailed

Used to consider compliance with standards as a fundamental building block for a secure ADS in the context of the argument. Arguments without normative specifications are therefore those for which there is currently no standard. Used to classify arguments.

Explanation

Normative reasoning contains positive reasoning about compliance with the norm. It is therefore argued that an AD system is secure because relevant standards are adhered to both during the development and operation of the AD system.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Object

Term German

Objekt

Intention

Description

Explanation

An object is the representation of a real object that influences the driving of a vehicle. Objects can be broken down into dynamic and static variants according to their usage in the various [scenario](#) layers.

Relation to other terms

Logical [scenarios](#), [scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Objective Argumentation

Term German

Objektive Argumentation

Intention

Evaluation

Intention detailed

Used to classify arguments.

Explanation

In contrast to the normative path, which argues for security in a positive sense by taking into account and adhering to the norm, the [objective](#) path provides appropriate evidence for the normative specifications but also for the operationalization from the argument. In addition, the [objective](#) path is used to address any [concerns](#) and substantiate them with appropriate evidence so that these [concerns](#) are considered refuted within the context under consideration.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Occlusion

Term German

Verdeckung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Occlusions are limitations of the [vehicle under test](#)'s perception that are caused by other traffic participants. An occlusion is a form of reinforcing factor.

Relation to other terms

Logical [scenarios](#), [scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Operational Concept

Term German

Operational Concept

Abbreviation

OpsCon

Intention

Description

Explanation

Description of a system based on its environment, the elements, their behaviour and their relationships to one another with a focus on what the system does (not how it does it) and why. The system's characteristics are described from the perspective of a higher-level observer (e.g. user, moderator and other participants, etc.).

Source

Systems Engineering Handbook, INCOSE 2015, Kap. 4.1.2.2 (aus ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148)

Usage

TP4 / TP 7 AG1 / SB1 Björn Filzek

Operational Design Domain

Term German

Operational Design Domain

Abbreviation

ODD

Intention

Description

Explanation

The operational design domain (ODD) is defined as the set of "operating conditions under which a given [system under test](#) (driving automation system) is designed to function, including all environmental, geographical and time-of-day restrictions and/or the requisite presence or absence of certain traffic or roadway characteristics".

The ODD is the scope within which a [system under test](#) is designed to operate.

Related objects

[System under test](#)

Related subjects

[Subject vehicle](#), traffic participants, traffic environment

Relation to other terms

General, traffic environment

Delimitation from

Traffic environment, application framework

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Operational Domain

Term German

Operational Domain

Intention

Description

Explanation

The operational domain is the traffic space that defines the limits of the ODD.

It includes all elements of the environment of an [Automated Driving System](#) (ADS) and their relationships with one another. [Scenarios](#) and allocated [parameter spaces](#) are a suitable means of description.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Organisational Capability

Term German

Fähigkeit (Organisation)

Intention

Naming

Explanation

An organisation's potential to achieve a desired effect (e.g. continuous product safety improvement) through a combination of ways and means along with specified measures.

Related subjects

Development organisation

Source

https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Enterprise_Capability_Management: https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Enterprise_Capability_Management

Usage

AP3.4

Output Generation

Term German

Ausspielung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Output generation refers to the data that was generated using the [database mechanics](#) and that serves as a basis for the [test concept](#).

Among other things, the output data includes logical [scenarios](#) in OpenSCENARIO or OpenDRIVE format, distributions for the parameters in the associated [parameter spaces](#), and assessment metric(s) with the associated pass/fail criteria. It is also possible to take account of constraints relating to the limits of the driving function (ODD), for example.

Relation to other terms

Input and output data

Source

Pegasus Glossar

Usage

TP1

Overtaking Side Swipe Challenger (F)

Term German

Schnellerer Abdränger (F)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The overtaking side swipe **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/**object** that was outside the vehicle path behind the VUT at the start of the **scenario** approaches the side of the VUT at the end of the **scenario**.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**, **Scenario** model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de), Systematic Identification of **Scenarios**: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Overtaking Turn into Path Challenger (C)

Term German

Überholender Einscherer (C)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The overtaking turn into path **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/**object** that was outside the vehicle path behind the VUT at the start of the **scenario** cuts in front of the VUT.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**, **scenario** model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de), Systematic Identification of **Scenarios**: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

PEGASUS Data Base System

Term German

PEGASUS-Datenbank

Intention

Description

Explanation

The PEGASUS database system consists of a database, the [processing chain](#), the [backend](#) and the [frontend](#). Users can access it via the [frontend](#) (of the database website).

Related objects

Database

Related subjects

Data

Relation to other terms

Database

Source

Projekt Pegasus: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/PDF-HZE/12_Testspezifikations-Datenbank.pdf

Usage

TP1

PEGASUS-Input Data Format

Term German

PEGASUS-Eingangsdatenformat

Intention

Description

Explanation

The **input data** format/PEGASUS format is a common format into which **input data** must be transformed before being uploaded into the database so that it can be **processed** by the **database mechanics**. Among other things, it defines the file format, the signal names and the naming conventions for surrounding vehicles. The signals are defined based on JSON files. The file format is MAT or HDF5.

Relation to other terms

Input and output data

Source

Project Pegasus: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/Pegasus-Abschlussveranstaltung/14_Scenario-Formats.pdf

Usage

TP1

Parameter Space

Term German

Parameterraum eines [Szenarios](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The parameter space describes the [scenario](#) parameter combinations within a logical [scenario](#) that appear in the test specifications.

Within the scope of this description, it is also possible to describe dependencies between the [scenario](#) parameters.

Relation to other terms

[Scenarios](#)

Source

Projekt Pegasus: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/PDF-HZE/11_Szenarienformate.pdf

Usage

TP1

Pass-/Fail-Criteria

Term German

Bestehenskriterien

Intention

Beurteilen

Explanation

Pass/fail criteria are the criteria that the [system under test](#) (or VUT) must meet within a concrete test case in order to pass.

Relation to other terms

Tests

Source

Project Pegasus: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/PDF-Symposium/10_Test-Concept-and-Test-Case-Allocation.pdf

Usage

TP1

Perception Algorithm

Term German

Perzeptionsalgorithmus

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Umbrella term for the complex [processing](#) logic used to interpret [measurement data](#) (e.g. neural networks)

Explanation

Algorithm for creating a [world model](#) from [measurement data](#).

Relation to other terms

[Perception chain](#)

Delimitation from

[Sensor](#)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Offis

Perception Chain

Term German

Perzeptionskette

Intention

Naming + describing

Intention detailed

Functional description of perception.

Explanation

Description of a data [processing](#) chain from information sources to the creation of a [world model](#).

Related objects

Perception, [sensor](#), [processing](#), [architecture](#)

Subject (addressee)

Architect, licensing, test

Relation to other terms

Perception

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2; Bosch / OFFIS, ZF

Perception Characteristic

Term German

Perzeptionscharakteristik

Intention

Naming + describing

Intention detailed

Subdivision of perception phenomena that lead to increased [criticality](#).

Explanation

Description of the performance of a [perception chain](#) or a part thereof.

Relation to other terms

Perception, [perception chain](#), [criticality phenomenon](#)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Offis

Perception Fault

Term German

Perzeptionsfehler

Intention

Naming + describing

Intention detailed

Possible cause of the emergence of increased [criticality](#) due to perception.

Explanation

Measurement or [processing](#) error in the [perception chain](#) that leads to a significant deviation between reality and the [world model](#).

Relation to other terms

Perception

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Bosch / OFFIS, ZF

Perception Under Test

Term German

Zu testende Perzeption bzw. Perception under Test

Abbreviation

PUT

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various data sources

Explanation

Software or algorithms under test that [process](#) "sensor(s) under test" raw data relating to [environment model](#) data.

Related objects

Algorithm, neural network

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Relation to other terms

[Perception chain](#) ([perception chain](#) can also include labelling)

Delimitation from

[Sensor\(s\)](#) under test

Source

Scholtes 2022: [Influencing Factors](#) on Radar-based Perception: <https://d-nb.info/1279396628/34>

Usage

AP2.4, TP6, TP7, TP8; ika

Perception Under Test Data

Term German

[Perception under Test](#) Daten

Abbreviation

PUT Data

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various types of data

Explanation

Data of the type "[environment model](#) data" from the source "[sensor\(s\)](#) under test".

Additional information: In VVM, this data can be generated from the SRD in two different ways: either with [perception algorithms](#) provided by the research partners or with [object](#) tracking or suchlike that is integrated into the [sensor\(s\)](#) under test by the manufacturer.

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Relation to other terms

[Perception under test](#), [perception chain](#)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

AP2.4, TP6, TP7, TP8; ika

Perfect Perception

Term German

Perfekte Perzeption

Intention

Naming + describing

Explanation

Idealised perception of the world that accurately includes all characteristics of the world from the past to the present moment. Corresponds to an all-knowing perspective (cf. Laplace's demon, causal determinism).

Relation to other terms

Perception, [perfect perception technology](#), [real perception technology](#)

Source

VVM internal

Perfect Perception Technology

Term German

[Perfekte Perzeptionstechnologie](#)

Intention

Naming + describing

Explanation

Perception based on the choice of a technology (e.g. camera, radar, etc.) that accurately converts all characteristics of the world that can be recorded by this technology into a [world model](#). Here, the primary physical effects that are relevant to the technology are idealised, and secondary distortion effects are abstracted away.

Relation to other terms

Perception, [perfect perception](#), [real perception technology](#)

Source

VVM internal

Performance Requirement

Term German

Performance [Requirement](#)

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Measurable criterion that identifies a quality attribute of a function or how well a functional [requirement](#) shall be accomplished.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765f:2017 3.2870

Phase

Term German

Phase

Intention

Description

Explanation

A phase is a subactivity in a [process](#) and is made up of at least one [task](#).

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

ISO 15288

Usage

TRACY / ProSTEP

Phenomenon

Term German

Phänomen

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

People do not work like video cameras; they perceive an event based on their experiences and interests. The event is experienced, and the experience is related to other circumstances or experiences of the person in question. The term "phenomenon" refers to the description of these circumstances and therefore the subjectivity in the traffic [scene](#). It follows from this that it is also necessary to identify the perceiving subjects when describing a phenomenon.

Explanation

Description of events in the world of traffic that correspond to a subjective experience. The description is not an [objective](#) record of all aspects of the event; rather, it is perceived or experienced by one or more people against the backdrop of their own interest or state. It is based on the subject's direct experience.

Example: As a pedestrian, I perceive cars differently than car drivers.

Related objects

Traffic [scene](#), simultaneity (coincidence) in traffic, behaviour of other people in traffic, unexpected events, things

Related subjects

Traffic participants of all means of transport and age groups

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researcher, traffic planner, [requirements](#) engineer

Relation to other terms

Coincidence, perception, [scene](#)

Delimitation from

Measurement. Recording. The record of the event is not [objective](#), nor does it include all measurable aspects.

Source

Mayer, Verena. Edmund Husserl (2008): Logische Untersuchungen: <https://doi.org/10.1524/9783050050133>

Usage

TP3

Physical Architecture

Term German

Physische [Architektur](#)

Intention

Naming

Explanation

A physical [architecture](#) is an arrangement of physical elements (system elements, including software and physical interfaces) that provides the design solution for a product, service or enterprise and is intended to satisfy logical [architecture](#) elements and system [requirements](#). The physical [architecture](#) is implemented through technologies.

Source

https://sebokwiki.org/wiki/Physical_Architecture: https://sebokwiki.org/wiki/Physical_Architecture

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Physical Design

Term German

Physikalisches Design

Intention

Description

Explanation

Physical implementation of the [technical design](#).

Technical components are described, but not implemented, in the [technical design](#).

- Example
 - Recognition performance for a functionality (e.g. perception) is functionally specified
 - [Technical design](#): selection of a suitable [sensor](#) technology (laser, radar) with interfaces (Ethernet, CAN) and [processing](#) (SOC, [processors](#))
 - Physical design: actually implemented component with serial number
 - Technical component

Source

ISO 15288 (for the term "design"; there is no source for "technical")

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Physical Domain

Term German

Physikalische Domäne

Intention

Description

Explanation

Consideration of the concrete implementation (configuration) that meets the technical [requirements](#) and implements the technical interfaces.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4/7 AG1/SB1

Plausibility

Term German

Plausibilität

Intention

Evaluation

Intention detailed

Plausibility is a criterion for assessing the justifiability of statements.

Explanation

A statement is classified as plausible if there is a (majority) consensus that its justification is logical, clear and comprehensible.

Related objects

Statement, [causality](#)

Related subjects

Evaluators, consensus

Subject (addressee)

[Accident](#) researchers, experts

Relation to other terms

[Causality](#), [causal relation](#), causal chain

Delimitation from

[Causality](#)

Source

<https://www.dwds.de/wb/plausibel>: <https://www.dwds.de/wb/plausibel>

Usage

TP2; OFFIS / Bosch, ZF

Points of Control/ Points of Observation

Term German

Points of Control/ Points of Observation

Intention

Naming

Explanation

An invariant point in a technical system divided into modules at which, in the test system, control or observation can be assigned to the implementation or tester. The role of a point of control and observation can change depending on the system section and [concern](#).

Source

IEC9647-1

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Probability of Occurrence

Term German

Wahrscheinlichkeit des Eintretens

Intention

Measurement

Intention detailed

Explanation

The probability of occurrence includes the **exposure** to a **hazardous** situation, the occurrence of a **hazardous** event and the possibility to avoid or limit the **harm**.

Related subjects

Subject **vehicle**, vehicle occupants, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

Risk, severity of **harm**, **hazard**

Source

[ISO/IEC Guide 51: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec:guide:51:ed-3:v1:en:term:3.9>]

Process

Term German

Prozess

Intention

Description

Explanation

The term "process" refers to a collection of activities that are together intended to bring about the achievement of [objectives](#) in a [project](#). The next-finer level in the process is described by [phases](#).

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

[https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Process_\(glossary\)](https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Process_(glossary)): [https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Process_\(glossary\)](https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Process_(glossary))

Usage

TRACY

Project

Term German

Projekt

Intention

Description

Explanation

The term "project" refers to an extensive but time-limited plan that is created to achieve a defined goal. One characteristic of a project is that it requires the performance of a series of different [tasks](#), which may be independent of one another.

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63711.html>

Usage

TRACY; ProSTEP

Proof of Release

Term German

Freigabenachweis

Intention

Naming

Explanation

The proof of release is an [assurance case](#) that requires the fulfilment of multiple, concrete, release-relevant top-level [claims](#) (not only in relation to safety). The [safety case](#) is therefore a necessary component of the proof of release but is not sufficient because, [claims](#) other than safety must also be fulfilled for release (conformity with traffic rules, positive balance of [risks](#)).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Quality Assumption

Term German

Güteannahme

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of reference and under [test data](#) without having to cite a data source or data type.

Explanation

Umbrella term for the categories "reference" or "ground truth" and "under test" for perception data.

Related objects

Any kind of perception data

Subject (addressee)

Test engineer, [requirements](#) engineer, [sensor](#) modellers, people who work with perception data

Relation to other terms

[Ground truth data](#), [environment model](#) data

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP8, AP2.4; ika

Quality Criteria

Term German

Gütekriterium

Intention

Beurteilen

Intention detailed

For judgements, it is necessary to know when the condition for a decision is met and when it is not.

Here: the value of a quality level that is consulted for a decision/condition.

Explanation

Quality criteria define distinguishing characteristics of a quality with respect to a condition, a decision or a set of circumstances. For example, a value must be below a certain level for release.

Related objects

Technical products

Subject (addressee)

Engineers, judges, licensing authority, all TPs

Relation to other terms

Quality level, quality,

Example: pass/fail criteria

Delimitation from

Capability, performance

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Bosch

Real Perception Technology

Term German

Reale Perzeptionstechnologie

Intention

Naming + describing

Explanation

Actual perception of the world, including secondary distortion effects that emerge due to a specific implementation of the technology.

Relation to other terms

Perception, [perfect perception](#), [perfect perception technology](#)

Source

VVM internal

Real World Layer

Term German

Real World Layer

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Differentiation between various perspectives on the SuT. The various perspectives are accompanied by different problem domains and/or solution spaces. By naming the layer in a current [task](#), it is therefore possible to avoid misunderstandings.

Explanation

The real world layer provides a perspective for describing activities in order to provide empirical evidence that continuously proves or disproves the validity of assumptions from the capability and [engineering layers](#) ("known unknowns") using the physical system in the real environment. In addition, unforeseeable developments/events in the open context that occur in the real environment ("unknown unknowns") are fed back into the development cycle in a controlled manner.

The artefacts of the real world layer provide the basis for an argument that addresses the interaction between the physical system and the real world and that argues why an acceptable residual [risk](#) exists regarding the validity of assumptions from the capability & [engineering layers](#).

Core aspects

- Delimitation from [engineering layer](#): Eng. → solution in controlled environment, real world → solution in real environment
- Test vehicle in real world (where vehicles drive is influenced by the manufacturer) vs deployed fleet (no influence on where vehicles drive)
 - Decisions as to where the test vehicle should drive are made and argued in the real world layer

Related objects

[System under Test](#)

Delimitation from

[Engineering layer](#), [capability layer](#), six layer model

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

Rear End Challenger (I)

Term German

Auffahrer (I)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The rear-end [challenger](#) is a logical [scenario](#) in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/[object](#) that was in the vehicle path behind the VUT at the start of the [scenario](#) approaches the rear of the VUT

Relation to other terms

Logical [scenarios](#), [scenario](#) model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN ([pegasusprojekt.de](https://www.pegasusprojekt.de)), Systematic Identification of [Scenarios](#): <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Rear End Turning Into Path Challenger (H)

Term German

Einscherender Auffahrer (H)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The rear end turning into path **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/**object** that was outside the vehicle path behind the VUT at the start of the **scenario** approaches the rear of the VUT at the end of the **scenario**.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**
Scenario model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de), Systematic Identification of **Scenarios**: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Replay2Sim

Term German

Replay2Sim

Intention

Description

Explanation

Replay2Sim is a tool that allows recorded real data to be transferred into a concrete **scenario** (**measurement data**, abstract **scenario** description) and directly into the output format.

Relation to other terms

Tests

Source

Pegasus **Project**: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/PDF-Symposium/21_Field-Test-Concept.pdf

Usage

TP1

Requirement

Term German

Anforderung

Intention

Description

Explanation

A requirement is a textual or model-based description of an expectation of a system that is being developed.

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

ISO 15288: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63711.html>

Usage

TRACY / ProSTEP

Risk

Term German

Risiko

Intention

Assessment

Intention detailed

Explanation

Combination of the **probability of occurrence** of **harm** and the **severity** of that **harm**

Note 1 to entry:

The **probability of occurrence** includes the **exposure** to a **hazardous** situation, the occurrence of a **hazardous** event and the possibility to avoid or limit the **harm**.

Related subjects

Subject vehicle, vehicle occupants, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

Metrics, risk, probability, **hazard**

Delimitation from

Threat, danger, **hazard**, **accident**

Source

[ISO/IEC Guide 51: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec:guide:51:ed-3:v1:en:term:3.9>]

Safety Argument

Term German

Sicherheitsargument

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

ISO 26262-10: 2018 Clause 5.3.1 "safety argument communicates the relationship between the evidence and the **objectives**. (...) Both the argument and the evidence are crucial elements of the **safety case**. An argument without supporting evidence is unfounded, and therefore unconvincing. Evidence without an argument is unexplained, resulting in a lack of clarity as to how the safety **objectives** have been satisfied. (...)

A safety argument that argues safety through direct appeal to features of the implemented item (e.g., the behaviour of a timing watchdog) is often termed a **product argument**. A safety argument that argues safety through appeal to features of the development and assessment **process** (e.g., the design notation adopted) is often termed a **process argument**. Both types of argument can be used to achieve a sound argument for the safety of the item where a **process** argument can be seen as providing the confidence in the evidence used in the product argument."

Explanation

Constructs a **safety case** (including **claims**, arguments, and evidence) that a particular **requirement** has been met. The resulting argument shows that evidence supports the **claims**.

Source

UL4600 Clause 4.2.4 "Argue": https://users.ece.cmu.edu/~koopman/pubs/191213_UL4600_VotingVersion.pdf

Usage

Core03

Safety Case

Term German

Sicherheitsnachweis

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

ISO 26262-10:2018 Clause 5.3.1: The purpose of a safety case is to provide a clear, comprehensive and defensible argument, supported by evidence, that an item is free from unreasonable **risk** when operated in an intended context.

The guidance given here focuses on the scope of ISO 26262.

There are three principal elements of a safety case, namely:

- The **safety goals** and related safety **requirements** (safety **objectives** of the item or element)
- The **safety argument**
- The ISO 26262 series of standards work products (i.e., the evidence).

Explanation

A structured argument, supported by a body of evidence, which provides a compelling, comprehensible, and valid case that a system is safe for a given application in a given environment.

Source

UL 4600 4.2.40 "Safety Case": https://users.ece.cmu.edu/~koopman/pubs/191213_UL4600_VotingVersion.pdf

Usage

Core03

Safety Goal

Term German

Sicherheitsziel

Intention detailed

Begriffsbeziehungen

Explanation

A safety goal is a top-level safety requirement as a result of the hazard analysis and risk assessment at the vehicle level.

Note: One safety goal can be related to several hazards, and several safety goals can be related to a single hazard. [ISO 26262-1:2018(en) Road vehicles — Functional safety — Part 1: Vocabulary 3.139]

Remark 1: A safety goal describes the direction of the search for measures to reduce the risk of a hazard.

Remark 2: With the help of a safety goal, a group of hazardous events can be bundled together and addressed jointly.

Related subjects

Subject vehicle, vehicle occupants, traffic participants, ADS

Relation to other terms

Hazard, hazardous event, safety requirement, risk

Delimitation from

Safety requirement, capability, top goal, sub-goal

Source

ISO 26262-1:2018(en) Road vehicles — Functional safety — Part 1: Vocabulary 3.139: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:26262:-1:ed-2:v1:en:term:3.139>

Usage

TP3 / TP4

Safety Relevant Traffic Event

Term German

Sicherheitsrelevantes Verkehrereignis

Intention

Description

Explanation

The term safety-relevant traffic event describes a real chronological sequence in road traffic that led to a critical situation, such as an emergency stop or a road traffic [accident](#).

Related objects

Traffic environment

Related subjects

Traffic participants, traffic environment

Relation to other terms

General, traffic environment

Delimitation from

Road traffic [accident](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#): https://confluence.vdali.de/display/VVM/Materialsammlung+VVM?preview=%2F9438252%2F9438263%2F20191208_PEGASUS+Glossar_1-01.pdf

Usage

TP1

Safety principle

Term German

Sicherheitsprinzip

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

Description of an implication ("if X, then Y") whose application supports the achievement of a [safety goal](#).

Explanation

Driving manoeuvres, courses of action or characteristics that reduce [criticality](#) in a class of [scenarios](#).

Related objects

Driving manoeuvre, courses of action, characteristic

Related subjects

Automated vehicle, traffic participant

Subject (addressee)

[Requirements](#) engineer, traffic participant, simulation engineer

Relation to other terms

[Causal relation](#), causal chain, [criticality](#), [safety goal](#), safety function

Delimitation from

[Causal relation](#), causal chain, [safety goal](#), safety function

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2; OFFIS, Bosch, ZF

Scenario

Term German

Szenario

Intention

Description

Explanation

A scenario is a description of the chronological development in a sequence of [scenes](#).

Each scenario begins with an initial [scene](#). Actions/events and goals/values can be defined in order to determine the development of the scenario over time. In contrast to a [scene](#) that describes a moment, a scenario describes a period of time.

Relation to other terms

Scenarios

Source

Ulbrich et al (2015): Definition der Begriffe [Szene](#) Situation und Szenario für das automatisierte Fahren: <https://www.uni-das.de/images/pdf/veroeffentlichungen/std-01-ulbrich.pdf>

Usage

TP1

Scenario Parameter

Term German

[Szenario](#)parameter

Intention

Description

Explanation

A [scenario](#) parameter is a value that is used to make a characteristic description of a [scenario](#) (e.g. the course of the trajectory).

Relation to other terms

[Scenarios](#)

Source

Pegasus [Project](#): <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/Pegasus-Abschlussveranstaltung/PEGASUS-Gesamtmethode.pdf>

Usage

TP1

Scenario-Defining Factor

Term German

Szenario-Definierender Faktor

Intention

Description

Explanation

Scenario-defining factors are parts of a [scenario](#) that define whether the [scenario](#) belongs to a [scenario](#) type/class. These can be defined on one or more layers. They do not include parts that, although they belong to a [scenario](#), do not define it. The [scenario](#)-defining factor specifies the boundaries of the section of continuous travel, in the case of extraction from [measurement data](#). Whether a [scenario](#) belongs to a class (especially a logical [scenario](#) class) can be clearly determined by considering the [scenario](#)-defining factor.

Example:

[Scenario](#) type/class "turn into path [challenger](#)": Here, the [scenario](#)-defining factor is the turn into path [challenger](#) that cuts in front of the [subject vehicle](#). Although other elements, such as [occlusions](#) or the road, etc., may be part of the [scenario](#), they do not constitute [scenario](#)-defining factors.

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP8

Scene

Term German

Szene

Intention

Description

Explanation

The term scene refers to a snapshot that incorporates the moving and stationary elements of the traffic environment, the self-representation of all actors and observers, and the relations between these elements.

Relation to other terms

[Scenarios](#)

Source

Ulbrich et al (2015): Definition der Begriffe Szene Situation und [Szenario](#) für das automatisierte Fahren: <https://www.uni-das.de/images/pdf/veroeffentlichungen/std-01-ulbrich.pdf>

Usage

TP1

Semi-Concrete Scenario

Term German

Semi-konkretes [Szenario](#)

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

The semi-concrete [scenario](#) is a means of representing the test results of the simulation runs. It describes a subspace that contains relevant, critical [scenarios](#), for example. This [scenario](#) subspace is assessed within the framework of the identification of [risks](#), which therefore includes all relevant, critical [scenario](#) subspaces of the simulation and assesses them both individually and in cumulative form.

Explanation

A semi-concrete [scenario](#) describes a partly parameterised model of the chronological sequence of [scenes](#) (logical [scenario](#)), which begins with a starting [scene](#). Unlike a logical [scenario](#), the semi-concrete [scenario](#) defines – either explicitly or via a restricted parameter range – at least one parameter that describes a safety-relevant traffic event.

Relation to other terms

[Scenarios](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Sensor

Term German

Sensor

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Abstract category for technical components (camera, lidar, radar, etc.)

Explanation

Technical component that records certain physical characteristics in its environment as a measured quantity.

Relation to other terms

[Perception chain](#)

Delimitation from

[Perception algorithm](#)

Source

Wikipedia: "Sensor": <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sensor>

Usage

Bosch, OFFIS

Sensor Fusion

Term German

[Sensorfusion](#)

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Naming a technical unit that combines information from [sensor](#) systems.

Explanation

Combination of various signals within the [perception chain](#) to create an integrated overall version.

Relation to other terms

[Sensor](#)

Delimitation from

[Sensor](#)

Source

Wikipedia: "Sensorfusion": <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sensordatenfusion>

Usage

Bosch, OFFIS

Sensor Raw Data Labels

Term German

[Sensorrohdaten-Labels](#)

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various data types

Explanation

The term [sensor](#) raw data labels refers to data that extends [sensor](#) raw data. These extensions consist of labels that are produced by humans or machines and that add previously unavailable semantic information to the raw [sensor](#) data. The format of the labels is adapted to the raw data format.

Examples:

- Segmentation of camera images pixel by pixel
- Classification of individual points in a point cloud

Additional information:

In formal terms, the raw [sensor](#) data itself is not contained in [sensor](#) raw data labels.

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Delimitation from

[Ground truth data](#)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP8; ika

Sensor Under Test Raw Data

Term German

[Sensorik](#) Under Test Rohdaten

Abbreviation

SRD

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various types of data

Explanation

Data of the type "[sensor](#) raw data" from the source "[sensor](#)(s) under test".

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP6, TP7; ika

Sensor Under Test Raw Data Labels

Term German

Sensorik Under Test Rohdaten-Labels

Abbreviation

SRD Labels

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various types of data

Explanation

Data of the type "sensor raw data labels" from the source "sensor(s) under test".

Additional information: In VVM, this can be an interim result of research partners that want to convert SRD into PUT data.

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP6, TP7; ika

Sensor(s) Under Test

Term German

Sensorik Under Test
bzw. zu Testende Sensorik

Abbreviation

SeUT

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various data sources.

Explanation

The term [sensor](#)(s) under test refers to the [sensor](#) technology that is to be tested, which may consist of one or more automotive environmental [sensors](#). In this context, "sensor technology" refers to the hardware and software used to generate [sensor](#) raw data.

Additional information: In VVM, the SeUT is specifically the [sensor](#) technology in installation positions of the AVL vehicle that are close to where they will be in production.

The SeUT cannot be a component of a source of [ground truth data](#).

The term [sensor](#)(s) under test can also be used to refer to [sensor](#) technology that is to be modelled.

Related objects

[Sensor](#) hardware, [sensor](#) firmware

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Delimitation from

[Perception under test](#); [vehicle top box](#)

Source

Scholtes 2022: [Influencing Factors](#) on Radar-based Perception: <https://d-nb.info/1279396628/34>

Usage

TP6/TP8; ika

Separation of Concerns

Term German

Separation of **Concerns**

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Architectural principle for resolving **concerns** by division into solution elements that can be assigned different organisational roles so that the resulting system is suitable for resolving the addressed **concerns**.

Source

Wikipedia: "Separation of **Concerns**": https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Separation_of_concerns

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Set of Scenario Parameters

Term German

[Szenario](#)parametersatz

Intention

Description

Explanation

A set of [scenario](#) parameters is a vector in which a concrete value is assigned to all parameters of a logical [scenario](#). It is a point in the [parameter space](#) or, in other words, a concrete [scenario](#). The values for existing [metrics](#) and existing criteria can also be added to set of [scenario](#) parameters.

Relation to other terms

[Scenarios](#)

Source

Pegasus [Project](#): <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/Pegasus-Abschlussveranstaltung/PEGASUS-Gesamtmethode.pdf>

Usage

TP1

Severity

Term German

Schadenschwere (für Sach- und Personenschäden)

Intention

Measurement

Intention detailed

Definition	Beispiel
Bedrohung (threat): mögliche Ursache eines unerwünschten Ereignisses, der einem System oder einer Organisation Schaden zufügen kann [ISO/TR 18638]	Steiles Gelände in der Nähe der Straßeneinführung bedroht die Unversehrtheit der Beteiligten
Gefahr (danger): gefährliche Situation, die, wenn sie nicht vermieden wird, zum Tod oder zu schweren Verletzungen führen kann [ISO 26513]	A: Steinschlaggefahr B: Gefahr von Eisglätte
Gefährdung (hazard): potential source of harm [ISO 26262, ...] (for a specific stakeholder)	Hz1A: Beschädigung der Fahrgastzelle durch herabfallende Steine Hz2A: Spurverlust & Verlassen der Fahrbahn durch Steine auf der Fahrbahn
Gefährliches Ereignis (hazardous event): combination of a hazard and an operational situation [ISO 26262]	He1H1A: Stein mit 100kg Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz während der Fahrt im Bereich des Fahrers He2H1A: Stein mit 1 kg Masse trifft Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz im Stillstand im Bereich des Befahrers
Schaden (harm): physische Verletzung oder Schädigung der Gesundheit von Personen oder der Beschädigung von Sachen [ISO/IEC Guide 51] <i>modified</i>	Verletzung der FZ-Massen durch 1. beschädigte Fahrgastzelle 2. Verlassen der Fahrbahn
Risiko (risk): Schadensmaß (maß) kombiniert mit Eintrittswahrscheinlichkeit [ISO/IEC Guide 51]	120 x Steinschläge (Jahr) 10 % große Steine mit Verletzungspotential Verkehrsdichte 1:10 Scheibengröße 1:10 => 0,12 Verletzungsfälle/Jahr
Unfall (accident): Eintritt eines Schadens durch ein ungeplantes Ereignis [ISO 24765]	Tatsächlich verletzte Personen durch herabfallende Steine, welche die Windschutzscheibe eines Fz durchschlagen haben.

Explanation

Estimate of the extent of **harm** to one or more individuals **or property** that can occur in a potentially **hazardous event**

Related subjects

Subject **vehicle**, vehicle occupants, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

Algorithms and **metrics**, **risk**, probability, **hazard**

Delimitation from

Harm

Source

[ISO 26262-1:2018]: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso:26262:-1:ed-2:v1:en:term:3.154>

Side Swipe Challenger (E)

Term German

Abdränger (E)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The side swipe **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/**object** that was alongside the VUT at the start of the **scenario** approaches the side of the VUT.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**, **scenario** model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de), Systematic Identification of **Scenarios**: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Simulated Ground Truth

Term German

Simulated Ground Truth

Abbreviation

SGT

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various types of data

Explanation

Data of the type "ground truth data" generated from a simulation.

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with information on traffic [scenes](#)

Relation to other terms

Aerial Ground Truth, [Infrastructure Ground Truth](#), Dynamic Ground Truth

Delimitation from

[World model](#), [vehicle top box](#) raw data labels, [environment model](#) data

Source

Pegasus [Project](#): <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP2,3,4,5,6,7,8; ika

Situation (Traffic-)

Term German

Situation (Verkehrs-)

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

This term is intended to help name and categorise a set of circumstances in the traffic [scene](#).

Explanation

A situation is a constellation in the traffic [scene](#) that conditions a decision. The situation can be viewed as a point in time; it is not a sequence of events

Related objects

Traffic [scene](#)

Related subjects

Traffic participants

Subject (addressee)

TP2 ([Criticality](#) analysis), TP3, TP4 (Functions), TP7 (Test), VVM

Relation to other terms

Traffic [scene](#)

Delimitation from

[Scenario](#), sequence of events

Source

Ulbrich et al (2015): Definition der Begriffe [Szene](#) Situation und [Szenario](#) für das automatisierte Fahren: <https://www.uni-das.de/images/pdf/veroeffentlichungen/std-01-ulbrich.pdf>

Usage

TP1

Slower Rear End Challenger (G)

Term German

Zurückfallender Auffahrer (G)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The slower rear end **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/**object** that was outside the vehicle path in front of the VUT at the start of the **scenario** approaches the rear of the VUT at the end of the **scenario**.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**, **scenario** model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de), Systematic Identification of **Scenarios**: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Slower Side Swipe Challenger (D)

Term German

Langsamere Abdränger (D)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The slower side swipe **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/**object** that was outside the vehicle path in front of the VUT at the start of the **scenario** approaches the side of the VUT at the end of the **scenario**.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**, **scenario** model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de): <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>, Systematic Identification of **Scenarios**

Usage

TP1

Slower Turn Into Path Challenger (B)

Term German

Langsamere Einscherer (B)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The slower turn into path **challenger** is a logical **scenario** in which, in relative terms, a vehicle/**object** that was outside the vehicle path in front of the VUT at the start of the **scenario** cuts in front of the **subject vehicle**.

Relation to other terms

Logical **scenarios**, **scenario** model

Source

Pegasus Method - pegasus-EN (pegasusprojekt.de), Systematic Identification of **Scenarios**: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Strategic Test Coverage

Term German

Strategische Testabdeckung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Describes the overall [coverage](#) of [safety goals](#) by comparing test results with the functional [quality criteria](#) and their weighting in the context of [safety argumentation](#).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Strategic Test Planning

Term German

Strategische [Testplanung](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Continuous [test planning](#) at the functional level to demonstrate the [safety goals](#) in accordance with [safety argumentation](#) through a combination of suitable [test methods](#). Produces [functional test specifications](#).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Subject Vehicle

Term German

Ego-Fahrzeug

Intention

Naming

Explanation

The subject vehicle is a [vehicle under test](#) (VUT).

Related objects

Subject vehicle

Related subjects

System components, traffic environment, [operational design domain](#)

Relation to other terms

Subject vehicle, general, automation function

Delimitation from

[System under Test](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Subject Vehicle Model

Term German

[Ego-Fahrzeug-Modell](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

The [subject vehicle](#) model represents the simulation model of the vehicle used by the [system under test](#) (HAF system) that is being developed.

The model includes all necessary aspects of the individual vehicle components that are relevant to the assessment of the [system under test](#) in the respective concrete [scenario](#) to the required level of accuracy (digital twin). As well as the vehicle behaviour and vehicle functions, these are typically vehicle dynamics, including steering, chassis and braking systems, as well as the drive train.

Related objects

[Subject vehicle](#)

Related subjects

System components, traffic environment, [operational design domain](#)

Relation to other terms

General, [subject vehicle](#), system components, automation function

Delimitation from

[Subject vehicle](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Subjective Argumentation

Term German

Subjektive Argumentation

Intention

Evaluation

Intention detailed

Used to address [concerns](#) about the reasoning but also about the way the system/V&V system is developed. Used to classify arguments.

Explanation

These are [claims](#) and assessments that could be relevant for the system. These subjective indications must be assessed for relevance and checked if relevant. Relevant [claims](#)/assessments are checked through [objectification](#) (see: [objective argumentation](#)).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

Core03

System Architecture

Term German

Systemarchitektur

Intention

Description

Explanation

Fundamental concepts or properties of a system in its environment embodied in its elements, relationships, and in the principles of its design and evolution.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2011 Systems and software engineering–[Architecture](#) description

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1 / Björn Filzek

System Capability

Term German

Fähigkeit (System)

Intention

Naming

Explanation

A system's potential to achieve a desired effect (e.g., [target behavior](#)) realized through a combination of ways and means along with specified measures.

Related subjects

Subject-vehicle

Source

https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Enterprise_Capability_Management: https://www.sebokwiki.org/wiki/Enterprise_Capability_Management

Usage

AP3.4

System Level

Term German

Systemebene

Intention

Description

Explanation

Describes an abstraction or integration level in the system [architecture](#) at which [requirements](#) are formulated or test results are aggregated. This division can be carried out in both the functional and the [technical domain](#). Note: The functional and technical system levels are not identical!

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

System Under Test

Term German

System Under Test

Abbreviation

SuT

Intention

Naming

Explanation

The "system under test" (SuT) is the system that is to undergo testing. The complexity of the SuT used depends on the tests that are to be carried out.

Related objects

The system to be tested

Related subjects

[Subject vehicle](#), system components

Relation to other terms

General, [subject vehicle](#)

Delimitation from

[Subject vehicle](#)

Source

system under test - ISTQB Glossary: https://glossary.istqb.org/en_US/term/system-under-test-2-1

Usage

TP1

Target Behavior

Term German

Sollverhalten

Intention

Description

Explanation

The target behaviour is the behaviour of an actor that is to be implemented in a [scenario](#)-specific context and is derived from legal, societal and ethical rules as well as safety mechanisms.

Source

Salem et al. (2022): Ein Beitrag zur durchgängigen, formalen Verhaltensspezifikation automatisierter Straßenfahrzeuge: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.07204>

Usage

Core03

Task

Term German

Aufgabe

Intention

Description

Explanation

A task describes a work order within a [phase](#). Tasks are therefore the smallest unit that defines a [process](#). A task can have predecessors and successors and concludes with its generated output.

Subject (addressee)

TRACY

Source

ISO 15288: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63711.html>

Usage

TRACY / ProSTEP

Technical Architecture

Term German

Technische [Architektur](#)

Intention

Description

Explanation

Representation of the structure of technical elements for implementing the allocated functional (and logical) [requirements](#) and associated interface descriptions

Source

Based on ISO 15288

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Technical Design

Term German

Technisches Design

Intention

Description

Explanation

Technical [architecture](#) supplemented with the technical [requirements](#) and the description of interfaces between the technical [architecture](#) elements

Source

ISO 15288, (4.1.16 for the term design)

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Technical Domain

Term German

Technische Domäne

Explanation

Domain for considering the technological solution that fulfils the functional (and logical) [requirements](#) and implements the functional (and logical) interfaces

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Technical Test Requirement

Term German

Technische Testanforderung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Technical [requirement](#) or expectation to be met by a test procedure.

Technical test [requirements](#) are derived from the functional test [requirements](#) based on the actually implemented [technical design](#) ([allocation](#) of functional test [requirements](#)).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Technical Test Specification

Term German

Technische Testbeschreibung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Detailed (complete, precise, verifiable) formulation to describe activities for determining characteristic technical properties according to the technical [requirements](#) for a specific use.

Among other things, the technical test specification includes:

- test prerequisites
- test procedure
- test end criteria
- parameters
- measured quantities
- number of repetitions

Source

Expansion of test specification Testspezifikation - ISTQB [Glossary](https://glossary.istqb.org/de_DE/term/testspezifikation-1): https://glossary.istqb.org/de_DE/term/testspezifikation-1

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Test Automation

Term German

Testautomatisierung

Intention

Description

Explanation

Test automation is a method for automatically generating and carrying out concrete test cases. These are created by deduction from the logical test case within a [parameter space](#).

Relation to other terms

Tests

Source

Pegasus Project: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/Pegasus-Abschlussveranstaltung/17_Test_Automation.pdf

Usage

TP1

Test Class

Term German

Testklasse

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Categorises [test methods](#) for specific purposes, e.g.:

- [verification](#) / [validation](#)
- positiv-/negative tests
- reveal emergences during development/in the field

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Test Concept

Term German

Testkonzept

Intention

Description

Explanation

The test concept specifies the operational environment (e.g. simulation, proving ground, field) in which the logical **scenarios** are tested, along with the associated parameter characteristics, as well as establishing **requirements** for these tests. For example, it is also possible to define the test sequence and to determine the relevance of individual tests and uncertainties.

The ODD of the **system under test** serves as the basis for, among other things, planning the scope of validity, the general procedure, specifying the implementation limits of the test environments, identifying resources and scheduling the planned tests. In addition, **risks** and inadequacies are described according to the choice of test environments.

Relation to other terms

Tests

Source

Pegasus **Project**: https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/files/tmpl/Pegasus-Abschlussveranstaltung/16_Test_Concept.pdf

Usage

TP1

Test Data

Term German

Testdaten

Intention

Description

Explanation

Data created or selected to satisfy the input [requirements](#) for executing one or more test cases, which can be defined in the [test plan](#), test case or test procedure.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 29119-2:2021 Software and systems engineering — Software testing — Part 2: Test [processes](#): <https://www.iso.org/standard/79428.html>

Test Instance

Term German

Testinstanz

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Concretisation of a generic test platform (HiL, SiL, proving ground, field) by application-oriented designation of specific parts thereof (e.g. simulation environment x, software y).

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Test Means

Term German

Testmittel

Intention

Naming

Explanation

All artefacts/testing tools needed to carry out tests, with [requirements](#) and other documents.

Source

ISTQB [glossary](https://www.testautomatisierung.org/testglossar-test-deutsch/): <https://www.testautomatisierung.org/testglossar-test-deutsch/>

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Test Method

Term German

Testmethode

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Describes a specific approach to obtaining [measurement data](#) that can be used to evaluate a [requirement](#) with regard to a specific quality (e.g. concrete individual test, SiL variation, continuous operation)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Test Plan

Term German

Testplan

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Organisational planning and/or scheduling of tests.

Source

ISTQB glossary: <https://www.testautomatisierung.org/testglossar-test-deutsch/>

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Test Tool

Term German

Testwerkzeug

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Describes a concrete technical aid that is needed to carry out tests (e.g. external reference [sensors](#), PC, etc.)

Source

ISTQB [glossary](#): <https://www.testautomatisierung.org/testglossar-test-deutsch/>

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1

Threat

Term German

Bedrohung

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Definition	Beispiel
Bedrohung (threat): mögliche Ursache eines unerwünschten Ereignisses, der einem System oder einer Organisation Schaden zufügen kann [ISO/TR 18638]	Steiles Gelände in der Nähe der Straßeneinführung bedroht die Unversehrtheit der Beteiligten
Gefahr (danger): gefährliche Situation, die, wenn sie nicht vermieden wird, zum Tod oder zu schweren Verletzungen führen kann [ISO 26513]	A: Steinschlaggefahr B: Gefahr von Eisglätte
Gefährdung (hazard): potential source of harm [ISO 26262, ...] (for a specific stakeholder)	Hz1A: Beschädigung der Fahrgastzelle durch herabfallende Steine Hz2A: Spurverlust & Verlassen der Fahrbahn durch Steine auf der Fahrbahn
Gefährliches Ereignis (hazardous event): combination of a hazard and an operational situation [ISO 26262]	Hs1H1A: Stein mit 100kg Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz während der Fahrt im Bereich des Fahrers Hs2H1A: Stein mit 1 kg Masse trifft Masse trifft die Frontscheibe eines Kfz im Stillstand im Bereich des Befahrers
Schaden (harm): physische Verletzung oder Schädigung der Gesundheit von Personen oder der Beschädigung von Sachen [ISO/IEC Guide 51] <i>modified</i>	Verletzung der FZ-Massen durch 1. beschädigte Fahrgastzelle 2. Verlassen der Fahrbahn
Risiko (risk): Schadensmaßmaß kombiniert mit Eintrittswahrscheinlichkeit [ISO/IEC Guide 51]	120 x Steinschläge (Jahr) 10 % große Steine mit Verletzungspotential Verkehrsdichte 1:10 Scheibengröße 1:10 => 0,12 Verletzungsfälle/Jahr
Unfall (accident): Eintritt eines Schadens durch ein ungeplantes Ereignis [ISO 24795]	Tatsächlich verletzte Personen durch herabfallende Steine, welche die Windschutzscheibe eines Fz durchschlagen haben.

Explanation

EN: potential cause of an unwanted incident that may result in **harm** to a system or organization

Related subjects

Subject vehicle, vehicle occupants, traffic participants

Relation to other terms

Danger, **accident**

Delimitation from

Danger, **hazard**, **risk**, **accident**

Source

[ISO/TR 18638]: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso:tr:18638:ed-1:v1:en:term:3.38>

Top Goals

Term German

Top Goals

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Top goals demand activities to realize expectations of stakeholders regarding the testing method & how the **test method** should be used to test an "autonomous driving system" (ADS) on a highly abstract level.

Top goals are systematically derived abstractions from expectations (**claims**). Abstractions of expectations are decomposed, classified, hierarchized and finally sorted.

Benefit of Top Goals:

- Completeness due to iterative and systematic **decomposition**.
- Efficiency due to early consideration (frontloading) of redundancies, contradictions & concretizations.

Example for redundancy assessment:

- Top Goal: Compliance with norms, rules
- Execution of norms/standards
 - NHTSA: Guidelines for V&V of ADAS
 - Ethics Committee: Also guidelines for V&V from ADAS
- Example commonality:
 - Vehicle must carry out minimum **risk** maneuvers if the situation in the ODD is no longer safe
- **Process** Top Goal Analysis:
 - **Claim** is superficially the same
 - Sorting of individual **claims**
 - Revealing differences
 - * Redundancies are revealed when no differences are found

Source

Tino Brade: How to derive "Top Goals" systematically; March 2022; https://www.vvm-projekt.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Mid-Term/Presentations/VVM_HZE_S1_P1_20220315_TopGoals.pdf; accessed 2023/08/15

Usage

Core03

Trace-Link

Term German

Trace-Link

Intention

Description

Explanation

Trace links define a relationship between two artefacts.

Relation to other terms

TRACY

Source

ISO 15288: <https://www.iso.org/standard/63711.html>

Usage

TRACY/ ProSTEP

Traffic Simulation Vehicle

Term German

Traffic Simulation Vehicle

Abbreviation

TSV

Intention

Description

Explanation

The term traffic simulation vehicle refers to all vehicles in a simulation/on the proving ground that surround the [vehicle under test](#) (e.g. [challengers](#), action-constraining vehicles, surrounding traffic).

Related objects

Traffic participants

Related subjects

[Subject vehicle](#), traffic participants, traffic environment

Relation to other terms

General, Traffic environment

Delimitation from

[Subject vehicle](#), [challenger](#)

Source

Pegasus [Projekt](#): 14. Test HAD-F: Simulation, Proving Ground, Real World Drive: <https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/pegasus-method>

Usage

TP1

Validation

Term German

Validierung

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Confirmation, through the provision of **objective** evidence, that the **requirements** for a specific intended use or application have been fulfilled.

Note 1 to entry: In a life cycle context, validation involves the set of activities for gaining confidence that a system is able to accomplish its intended use, goals, and **objectives** in an environment like the operational environment. The right system was built.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2023(en): Systems and software engineering — System life cycle **processes** 3:54: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso-iec-ieee:15288:ed-2:v1:en>

Vehicle Top Box

Term German

Fahrzeug-Dachbox

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various data sources (data sources according to data table).

Explanation

The vehicle top box is a vehicle-mounted apparatus containing highly accurate [sensors](#).

Additional information: In VVM, it is located on the AVL vehicle.

Its purpose is to record "[sensor](#) raw data", which is used to create a "Dynamic Ground Truth" (DGT).

Related objects

[Sensor](#) hardware, [sensor](#) firmware

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Delimitation from

[Sensor\(s\)](#) under test

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP6 / ika

Vehicle Topbox Raw Data

Term German

[Fahrzeug-Dachbox](#) Rohdaten

Abbreviation

TRD

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various types of data

Explanation

Data of the type "[sensor](#) raw data" from the source "[vehicle top box](#)".

Additional information: In VVM, this is an input to understand.AI for determining the "Dynamic Ground Truth" (DGT).

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP6; ika

Vehicle Topbox Raw Data Labels

Term German

[Fahrzeug-Dachbox](#) Rohdaten-Labels

Abbreviation

TRD Labels

Intention

Naming

Intention detailed

Differentiation of various types of data

Explanation

Data of the type "[sensor](#) raw data labels" from the source "[vehicle top box](#)"

Additional information: In VVM, this is an interim result of understand.AI for determining the "Dynamic Ground Truth" (DGT).

Related objects

Traffic environment

Subject (addressee)

People who work with perception data

Delimitation from

Dynamic Ground Truth

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP6; ika

Vehicle Under Test

Term German

Vehicle Under Test

Abbreviation

VUT

Intention

Description

Explanation

The vehicle under test (VUT) is a vehicle whose automated driving function is being tested.

Data recorded by a VUT describes the traffic situation from its perspective relative to its own state.

Related objects

[Subject vehicle](#)

Related subjects

System component, traffic environments, [operational design domain](#)

Relation to other terms

[Subject vehicle](#), general, automation function

Delimitation from

[System under test](#)

Source

Pegasus [glossary](#)

Usage

TP1

Verification

Term German

Verifikation

Intention

Naming

Explanation

Confirmation, through the provision of **objective** evidence, that specified **requirements** have been fulfilled.

Note 1 to entry: Verification is a set of activities that compares a system or system element against the required characteristics. This includes, but is not limited to, specified **requirements**, design description, and the system itself. The system was built right.

Source

ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2023(en): Systems and software engineering — System life cycle **processes** 3:55: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso-iec-ieee:15288:ed-2:v1:en>

World Model

Term German

Weltmodell

Intention

Description

Intention detailed

The aim of a world model is to describe the [objects](#)/states/characteristics/phenomena that are relevant to the application.

Explanation

Representation of the environment based on perception and one's own state.

Related objects

Automation, simulation

Related subjects

Experts

Subject (addressee)

Licence, law

Relation to other terms

Perception

Delimitation from

[Environment model](#)

Source

VVM internal

Usage

TP2/ Bosch / OFFIS, ZF

Zig-Zag Model

Term German

Zig-Zag Model

Intention

Description

Explanation

The zig-zag model is an exemplary description of how [architectures](#) are defined, [requirements](#) are decomposed and interfaces are described recursively over various [system levels](#).

[Requirements](#) for the elements of the subordinate layer (white box) are derived from black-box [requirements](#) from the higher [system level](#), resulting in new black-box [requirements](#) for the next [system level](#).

Source

VVM Intern: AG1 Präsentationen: <https://confluence.vdali.de/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=10618852> System [Architecture](#) & Design Definition

Direkt Link pptx: <https://confluence.vdali.de/download/attachments/10618852/System%20Architecture%20and%20Design%20Definition.pptx?version=3&modificationDate=1661941683296&api=v2>

Usage

TP4 / TP7 AG1 / SB1